

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF A GENETIC
SEXING STRAIN FOR THE CONTROL OF
THE ASIAN TIGER MOSQUITO**

Thesis for the degree of "Doctor of Philosophy" by

Doron Shalom Yishai Zaada

Submitted to the Senate of the Hebrew University of
Jerusalem

October 2025

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This work was carried out under the supervision of:

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Είμαι από το χωριό, δεν ξέρω τίποτα.

Abstract

Mosquitoes remain among the most dangerous disease vectors globally, and male mosquitoes are increasingly being released in control programs as self-dispersing agents of population suppression. A critical bottleneck for these strategies is sex separation: the ability to reliably and efficiently isolate males from the vast numbers of insects produced in mass-rearing facilities. In *Aedes* mosquitoes, this is typically achieved mechanically at late developmental stages, requiring skilled personnel or high-cost automated systems. Genetic sexing strains (GSS), which allow early-stage separation by coupling a selectable trait to one sex, are regarded as a scalable alternative. However, classical GSS development has depended on random mutagenesis and rare chromosomal rearrangements, making success unpredictable and species-specific.

In this work, a rational, genome-engineering-based approach was established to generate a GSS in the Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus*. The pigmentation gene *yellow* was selected as a robust visual marker, and a loss-of-function allele producing a bright yellow phenotype throughout development was generated using CRISPR-Cas9 without major fitness effects other than severe egg desiccation sensitivity. Wild-type pigmentation and egg viability were restored through the introduction of a synthetic rescue cassette expressing *yellow* under the *hsp83* promoter.

To achieve male-specific pigmentation, the male-determining region surrounding *nix* was surveyed, and male-exclusive genomic sites were computationally identified. Although targeted transgene insertion into four candidates was not achieved, incorporation of *nix* into the *yellow* rescue cassette resulted in complete female-to-male phenotypic conversion. Consequently, a GSS strain was obtained in which only (pseudo-)males displayed wild-type pigmentation, while females remained yellow.

The suitability of this GSS for operational use was subsequently evaluated. Compared with the wild type, GSS males exhibited no developmental or size disadvantages. Yellow females were slightly larger and developed more slowly, reducing their proportion among pupating larvae. The vivid, sex-specific phenotype greatly improved both the accuracy and speed of the sexing process. In mating assays, pseudomales of the GSS performed comparably to wild-type males in locating and intercepting females for courtship and in their ability to induce female post-mating refractoriness, although they were less preferred by females.

Overall, a predictable, engineering-based route for constructing GSS in non-model organisms was demonstrated. This development provides a field-relevant platform for scalable male production and lays the foundation for a transferable framework for developing genetic sex-separation systems in other vector species, advancing sustainable genetic control technologies.

A letter of contribution:

This dissertation represents original research conceived by Doron Zaada under the supervision of Dr. Philippos Papathanos at the Department of Entomology, The Robert H. Smith Faculty of Agriculture, Food and Environment, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem (HUJI).

D. Zaada was responsible for the conception, experimental design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and writing of all research described in this work, unless otherwise specified.

Collaborative input was limited to scientific discussion and technical support, as detailed below:

- Mosquito colony maintenance and routine screening:
O. Toren, N. Galpaz, D. Gildman, S. Kehat, D. Perets, G. Ostrovsky, G. Ens.
- Bioinformatic pipeline:
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- Assistance in pupal imaging for morphometric analysis:
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This dissertation is presented as a monograph and contains original material that has not been previously submitted for another degree.

Philippos Papathanos

Doron Zaada

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General Introduction

1.1. Global importance of *Aedes albopictus*

Among approximately 3,600 described mosquito species (Diptera: Culicidae), only a small fraction threatens human health (Yee et al, 2022). Within this group, it is the blood-feeding females that acquire and transmit pathogens responsible for debilitating and sometimes fatal diseases (Foster & Walker, 2019). Among the medically important species, *Aedes albopictus* (aka the Asian tiger mosquito) has emerged as the most invasive and widely distributed (Piccinno et al., 2025).

Originally confined to Southeast Asia, *Aedes albopictus* has now become established across tropical, subtropical, and temperate regions worldwide (Nie & Feng, 2023). Its spread has been facilitated by human trade, particularly through the transport of its desiccation-resistant eggs, and by its adaptability to diverse climates and urban environments (Benedict et al., 2007; Swan et al., 2022). Although its flight range is limited (Vavassori et al., 2019), these ecological and behavioral traits have made *Ae. albopictus* a remarkably successful invader. *Ae. albopictus* diverged from its close relative *Ae. aegypti* about 31 million years ago, yet both species share a high capacity to transmit arboviruses such as dengue, chikungunya, Zika, and yellow fever (Soghigian et al., 2023). Despite this shared vector competence, the two species differ markedly in feeding behavior and host preference. *Ae. aegypti* is highly anthropophilic, feeding almost exclusively on humans and breeding predominantly in domestic water-holding containers in close association with human habitation (Powell & Tabachnick, 2013). In contrast, *Ae. albopictus* is more opportunistic, feeding on a broader range of vertebrate hosts including birds, mammals, and humans, and exploiting both urban and peri-urban breeding sites (Faraji et al., 2014). This broader host and habitat range was thought to reduce the frequency of human-biting events and the per-bite probability of human infection, which historically led to *Ae. albopictus* being regarded as a vector of secondary importance compared with *Ae. aegypti* (Faraji et al., 2014; Sindhanja et al., 2025). This disparity in focus is rooted not only in ecological traits but also in historical context: *Ae. aegypti* began colonizing the Americas approximately 500 years ago (Powell &

Tabachnick, 2013), and its pivotal role in yellow-fever transmission established it early on as the archetype for mosquito-borne disease research (Reed et al., 1900).

However, the global distribution of *Ae. albopictus* expanded dramatically during the late twentieth century, coinciding with increased international trade and urbanization. This expansion marked a transition in its epidemiological significance. Formerly regarded as a secondary vector, *Ae. albopictus* garnered increased scientific attention after exhibiting the capacity to sustain arboviral transmission beyond tropical zones. The 2007 chikungunya outbreak in Italy, which resulted in over 200 confirmed cases, provided the first clear evidence that *Ae. albopictus* alone can trigger epidemics in temperate regions (Rezza et al., 2007). It was later implicated in the 2014 dengue outbreak in Japan marking the first local transmission in over 70 years (Kutsuna et al., 2015), and contributed to the spread of Zika across the Americas between 2015 and 2016 (Azar et al., 2017; Boyer et al., 2018). The ongoing expansion of Aedes mosquito populations is amplifying the global threat of arboviral infections, fostering hyperendemic conditions and facilitating the simultaneous circulation of multiple arboviral disease outbreaks (Rückert et al., 2017; Messina et al., 2019, 2019; Wiyono et al., 2021).

1.2 Conventional Mosquito Control Strategies

With no effective vaccines available for most arboviral infections, vector control remains the main strategy for preventing disease outbreaks (Weaver & Reisen, 2010). Mosquito control methods are generally classified as physical, biological, chemical, or genetic (Achee et al., 2015). Unfortunately, none of these provides a fully effective or sustainable solution for *Ae. albopictus* (Baldacchino et al., 2015).

Physical control aims to remove or deny access to aquatic habitats required for egg laying and larval development. Typical approaches include eliminating stagnant water containers or using oviposition traps that attract females to lay eggs but are discarded before larvae mature (Jaffal et al., 2023). These methods depend on accurately locating breeding sites, which is difficult given the cryptic and opportunistic oviposition behavior of *Ae. albopictus* (Abramides et al., 2011). This

species readily exploits small and transient water sources, hindering the overall effectiveness of source-reduction efforts (Benedict et al., 2007).

Biological control relies on natural predators, parasites, or pathogens, most of which exert their effects during the larval stage of the mosquito life cycle. Notable examples include larvivorous fish such as *Gambusia affinis* and the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis israelensis* (Bti), which produces mosquito-specific toxins (Benelli et al., 2016). Although environmentally friendly, these agents require repeated applications or permanent aquatic habitats to maintain efficacy.

Chemical control remains the most widely used method, employing fast-acting insecticides such as organophosphates, pyrethroids, and temephos to target larvae or adults (Karunaratne et al., 2013; N. Liu, 2015). However, extensive and repeated applications of these insecticides have selected for resistance across multiple chemical classes, undermining effectiveness (L. B. Smith et al., 2016; Q. Liu et al., 2024; Schmidt et al., 2024). Chemical control also carries ecological and health concerns, including impacts on pollinators, aquatic organisms, and risks associated with chronic human exposure (Nicolopoulou-Stamati et al., 2016; Qi et al., 2022).

1.3. Genetic control

Genetic control is a population-management strategy that suppresses or replaces wild insect populations through the release of modified individuals. In suppression programs, the released insects are typically autocidal: sterilized or genetically engineered males that, after mating with wild females, produce non-viable or sterile offspring, thereby reducing the population's reproductive capacity (Knippling, 1955; Alphey, 2014). The effectiveness of genetic control capitalises the intrinsic reproductive asymmetry between males and females. Males can mate repeatedly with minimal physiological cost, whereas females invest substantial resources in egg production and have limited mating receptivity and reproductive capacity. As a result, females represent the limiting factor that determines population size. Consequently, mating with a non-reproductive male can drastically reduce a female's reproductive potential (Lance & McInnis, 2021).

Genetic control differs from conventional control in both its delivery and its operational logic (Whitten & Mahon, 2006). Physical, biological, and chemical interventions depend on locating breeding sites or pest concentrations and act by killing or severely impairing the target organisms. In genetic control, the released males disperse on their own, locate wild females, and transmit sterility or genetic changes through mating, circumventing the need to identify or treat breeding habitats directly (Bourtzis & Vreysen, 2021; Marec et al., 2021). The objective of genetic control is not to eliminate the released insects, but to maintain their vigor and mating competitiveness. Its success relies on the survival, dispersal, and sexual performance of these males, which must outnumber and match rival their wild counterparts to secure effective mating. In this sense, GC reverses the logic of conventional control: instead of seeking to immediately eradicate the pest, it maximizes the fitness of the released individuals to suppress the population through reproduction interference. Because suppression arises from species-specific mating interactions rather than broad chemical or mechanical interventions, genetic control provides a selective and environmentally compatible approach to mosquito control. It minimizes impacts on non-target organisms and avoids environmental contamination while remaining effective across wide areas through self-dispersal of the autocidal trait (Benedict, 2021).

The best-known example of genetic control is the Sterile Insect Technique (SIT), which relies on the continuous mass release of irradiated insects. The irradiation process mainly damages the genetic material of actively dividing gametes within reproductive organs, making them far more susceptible than the differentiated, non-dividing cells of somatic tissues (Bakri et al., 2021). As a result, sterilized insects remain sexually active and capable of mating with wild conspecifics, but they transfer genetically damaged gametes that fail to produce viable zygotes. Continuous releases of sterile individuals progressively reduces the number of fertile matings within the target population. As population density declines, the ratio of sterile to fertile individuals increases, amplifying the suppressive effect and potentially leading to population collapse and even eradication (Bourtzis & Vreysen, 2021) .

1.4. The Challenges in Mosquito Genetic control

Since its debut in the 1950s, the Sterile Insect Technique (SIT) has achieved major success in controlling agricultural pests. Landmark programs led to the eradication of the New World screwworm (*Cochliomyia hominivorax*) and the pink bollworm (*Pectinophora gossypiella*) from North America (Bushland et al., 1955; Tabashnik et al., 2021). SIT has also been widely implemented against the Mediterranean fruit fly (*Ceratitis capitata*), where sustained releases have suppressed populations on national and regional scales (Enkerlin, 2021). These successes established SIT as a reliable and effective strategy for pest population suppression.

For SIT to function effectively, two main conditions must be met: the released males must remain sexually competitive to mate with wild females, and their release must not create medical, ecological, or economic risks. Meeting these conditions is relatively straightforward in agricultural pests, where the damaging stage is larval and adult releases take place in rural environments. In mosquitoes, however, both requirements are more difficult to satisfy. The adult stage is responsible for disease transmission, and releases occur in densely populated urban or peri-urban settings, where any accidental release of females poses nuisance public-health concerns (Knipling et al., 1968).

Encouraged by SIT's success in agriculture, researchers have attempted since the early 1960s to adapt the method for mosquitoes. Large-scale trials targeting *Ae. aegypti* (Morlan et al., 1962) and *Anopheles quadrimaculatus* (Weidhaas et al., 1962) were among the first efforts. Despite their ambitious scope, these interventions produced no measurable reduction in population density, female fecundity, or egg-hatch rate. Subsequent small-scale studies that have tested alternative sterilization methods and achieved only limited success (Lofgren et al., 1974; McDonald et al., 1977).

These early trials revealed two major challenges that have continued to hinder mosquito SIT. First, compared with other agricultural pests, mosquitoes are more sensitive to handling and transportation, which compromises the mating competitiveness of released males (Wilke & Marelli, 2012; Maïga et al., 2023). This

reduction in field performance necessitates increased production volumes to achieve effective suppression (Barclay, 2021). Second, the need to eliminate females prior to release introduced an additional production step that reduced efficiency and limited scalability. Together, these constraints made it difficult to ensure effective large-scale, male-only releases and ultimately stalled mosquito SIT deployment, leaving the field largely dormant for more than three decades (Lees et al., 2015; Klassen et al., 2021).

1.5. Contemporary Mosquito Genetic Control Strategies

The 2007 chikungunya outbreak in Italy marks a turning point in mosquito genetic control field trials. That same year, an Italian research team reported results from an SIT pilot trial against *Ae. albopictus*, demonstrating a significant reduction in egg hatch rates despite a relatively small number of released males (Bellini et al., 2007). This success revitalized mosquito SIT program deployment and stimulated efforts to improve the competitiveness of released males while developing more efficient sex-sorting technologies. Consequently, optimization of rearing conditions and refinements in sterilization protocols became major focuses, accompanied by the exploration of alternative suppression methods that do not rely on irradiation. Two such approaches, the Release of Insects carrying Dominant Lethal genes (RIDL) and the Incompatible Insect Technique (IIT), emerged as promising alternatives. Unlike SIT, both involve the release of fertile males, achieving population suppression through different mechanisms.

The RIDL system, originally developed in *Drosophila* (Thomas et al., 2000), employs a transgenic construct expressing a female-specific toxin regulated by a bacterial-derived tetracycline-repressible transactivator (tTA). During mass rearing, tetracycline is continuously supplied to suppress toxin expression, allowing females to survive for colony maintenance and egg production (Harris et al., 2012). In contrast, tetracycline is withheld from the release generation, ensuring that only males develop to adulthood (Spinner et al., 2022). When wild females mate with RIDL males, they produce no viable daughters, and half of the surviving male offspring inherit the female-lethal transgene, amplifying the suppressive effect over

successive generations. This approach has been applied to several pest species, including *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus*, offering three major advantages over traditional SIT. It enables male-only releases, preserves the fitness of released males, and enhances suppression efficiency (Labbé et al., 2012; Carvalho et al., 2015). Despite these advantages, the deployment of a transgene-based system that propagates within wild populations has faced substantial regulatory and public resistance. Nearly twenty years passed between the development of the *Ae. aegypti* OX513A strain and its eventual approval for use in the United States, raising doubts about the near-term feasibility of implementing a similar approach for *Ae. albopictus* (St. Leger, 2021).

In contrast to the transgenic nature of RIDL, the Incompatible Insect Technique (IIT) exploits naturally occurring intercellular bacterial symbionts. *Wolbachia* bacteria spread through arthropod populations by manipulating host reproduction, most notably through cytoplasmic incompatibility (CI), a phenomenon in which matings between infected males and uninfected females yield nonviable offspring. CI was first described in *Culex quinquefasciatus* and was later used successfully for population suppression and eradication in Myanmar (Laven, 1967). To extend this principle to other species, researchers developed methods to artificially introduce *Wolbachia* infections across hosts. *Ae. albopictus* was the first mosquito successfully transfected with a *Culex pipiens*-derived *Wolbachia* strain (*wPip*) via embryo microinjection (Calvitti et al., 2012). Mating between *wPip*-infected released males and wild uninfected females leads to complete embryonic arrest, causing effective population suppression. Because IIT eliminates the need for irradiation, released males remain more sexually competitive than their SIT counterparts (Atyame et al., 2016). However, the approach requires exceptionally stringent sex-sorting, since the accidental release of even a small number of *Wolbachia*-infected females could establish a self-sustaining population that becomes refractory to suppression.

Current *Ae. albopictus* control programs often use SIT, IIT, or a combination of both (Puggioli et al., 2016). Notably, the first documented eradication of *Ae. albopictus* was achieved using a hybrid SIT-IIT strategy (X. Zheng et al., 2019). In this approach, *Wolbachia*-infected mosquitoes were exposed to low-dose irradiation sufficient to sterilize females while minimally affecting male fitness. The integrated

strategy alleviated the stringent sex-sorting and quality-control requirements of standalone IIT, improving production efficiency. Nevertheless, the need to eliminate nearly all females prior to release remains a critical limitation, constraining scalability. Despite three years of sustained effort, eradication was achieved only on a small island measuring 0.33 km², underscoring the logistical challenges of applying these methods to larger, more complex, or connected environments.

1.6 Available Sex Separation Solutions for *Aedes* Mosquitoes

The process of separating males and females before release, termed sexing, is a mandatory requirement for suppressive mosquito genetic control programs. Effective sexing enables the exclusive release of males, which are responsible for driving population suppression, while retaining the biting females within the production facilities, where they remain essential for colony maintenance and egg production (Lutrat et al., 2019).

In *Aedes* mosquitoes, sexing typically relies on morphological and developmental differences between males and females that become apparent during the pupal stage. Male *Aedes* larvae pupate earlier and produce smaller pupae than females. These two characteristics, timing and size, are commonly used to separate the sexes. Collecting pupae soon after pupation yields a cohort dominated by males, which can then be subjected to mechanical size separation using sieves or specialized devices. The classical glass separator, developed by Fay and Morlan (1962) and employed in early *Aedes* SIT programs, remains the benchmark for sexing efficiency. In this system, pupae slide between two inclined glass plates with a narrowing gap; smaller male pupae pass through while larger females are retained (Focks, 1980). This straightforward design, capable of producing approximately one million male pupae per week, remains the standard for sexing in *Aedes* genetic control programs (Malfacini et al., 2022). However, despite its effectiveness, manual operation is laborious and not scalable, and such methods can only support small and spatially confined pilot trials (Zheng et al., 2019; Zeng et al., 2022; Balatsos et al., 2024).

To overcome these limitations, automated size-based robotic systems have been developed to replace manual sexing, offering a 10- to 17-fold increase in production capacity and improved sorting precision (Gong et al., 2024). Beyond size-based approaches, sex can also be inferred from morphological features. Male pupae can be distinguished by the presence of terminal claspers, and adult males exhibit plumose antennae and elongated maxillary palps, whereas females have pilose antennae and shorter palps. Advances in image analysis and machine learning have produced systems capable of identifying these traits automatically. Although current

published data mainly concern *Ae. aegypti* (Crawford et al., 2020), similar technologies are being developed for *Ae. albopictus* (*Diptera.Ai*, 2025; *Senecio Robotics*, 2025). The introduction of these automated systems has substantially increased production throughput and now supports *Ae. aegypti* genetic control interventions in non-isolated urban districts ranging from 2 km² (Crawford et al., 2020) to 10 km² (Bansal et al., 2024). However, such systems do not always guarantee high male recovery rates (Malfacini et al., 2023), and attempts to apply them to *Ae. albopictus* can damage sorted pupae, impairing the flight capability of released males (Mamai et al., 2024). Furthermore, sorting remains limited to late developmental stages and requires specialized mechanical or optical equipment. These constraints continue to hinder large-scale production, and sexing remains a major bottleneck in most mosquito genetic control programs.

1.7 Genetic Sexing Strains

Despite recent advances in the field, efficient sexing remains a major challenge in deploying genetic control strategies. Genetic sexing strains (GSSs) offer an effective, economical, and scalable solution to this problem (Papathanos et al., 2018). GSSs are insect strains whose genetics have been manipulated to link a selectable trait exclusively to one sex. This linkage between sex and phenotype can be achieved by translocating genetic material to a sex chromosome. Genetic translocation is an irradiation-induced process in which ionizing radiation creates random double-strand DNA breaks across different chromosomes. During repair, non-homologous segments may fuse incorrectly, generating chimeric chromosomes and establishing new genetic linkages between previously unassociated genes (Muller & Altenburg, 1930). In the case of sex chromosomes, this process can result in a linkage between the sex-determining factor and a gene that was previously located on an autosome.

Early GSS development exploited naturally occurring, well-characterized insecticide-resistance alleles. These dominant gain-of-function alleles allowed strong selection and could be readily screened in laboratory settings. The first successful GSS was generated by translocating a dieldrin-resistance allele to the Y chromosome of *Anopheles gambiae*, enabling selective elimination of females at the

larval stage through dieldrin exposure (Curtis et al., 1976). Similar approaches were later applied to other mosquito species using dieldrin, propoxur, and malathion (Lowe et al., 1981; Shetty, 1987; Sanil & Shetty, 2010; Yamada et al., 2012). However, these solutions remained largely experimental proof-of-concept rather than a practical suppression tool. Their adoption was hindered by substantial fitness costs in surviving males, the risk of partially fertile males spreading resistance alleles to wild populations, and safety concerns arising from continuous pesticide exposure in rearing facilities and the environmental accumulation of residues during mass releases (Jorgenson, 2001; Yamada et al., 2013).

Advances in insect transgenesis enabled the stable integration of foreign DNA into the mosquito germline, allowing the development of male-specific traits without the disruptive chromosomal rearrangements associated with traditional translocation (Häcker et al., 2021). A major advantage of transgenesis is its high transferability. Similar constructs can often be applied to related species with minimal modification, producing comparable outcomes. One approach uses synthetic constructs driven by $\beta 2$ -*tubulin* testis-specific promoters to express a fluorescent protein, facilitating early identification of male third-instar larvae at the onset of spermatogenesis (Catteruccia et al., 2005; Smith et al., 2007). More recent systems employ conserved sex-specific intron motifs to achieve differential splicing of ubiquitously expressed fluorescent markers, permitting even earlier selection of male individuals (Weng et al., 2023, 2024). Another strategy exploits the random integration of transposon-mediated transgenesis to isolate lines in which a ubiquitous marker is inserted by chance into a sex chromosome (Volohonsky et al., 2015). Lutrat *et al.* (2023) further demonstrated that crossing two transgenic lines carrying male- and female-specific markers can produce a non-transgenic male cohort suitable for release. A related single-strain approach was later developed for *Aedes aegypti* (Compton et al., 2025). These strategies are particularly valuable given the regulatory and public acceptance barriers that limit the release of transgenic insects. Another common limitation of these contemporary transgenic GSS solutions is their reliance on fluorescent markers, which necessitate additional and often costly infrastructure, such as large-particle flow cytometers, to achieve sex separation at scale. All *Aedes* GSSs developed to date are summarized below **[Table 1.1]**.

In contrast to dominant gain-of-function mutations or fluorescent markers, recessive loss-of-function mutations provide an alternative approach for GSS development without the need for insecticides or specialized optics. This approach is exemplified by the VIENNA 8 strain of the Mediterranean fruit fly, the most successful GSS developed to date (Franz, 2005; Franz et al., 2021). The VIENNA 8 strain serves as a base strain from which several operational variants have been derived for use in large-scale SIT programs worldwide (Rempoulakis et al., 2016). The strain incorporates two recessive mutations: *white pupae (wp)*, which causes white pupal coloration, and *temperature-sensitive lethal (tsl)*, which renders individuals intolerant to elevated temperatures. A successful translocation event moved the functional dominant alleles of these genes to the Y chromosome, and the introduction of this chimeric chromosome into a background of homozygous mutant females produced a GSS in which only males exhibit wild-type phenotypes, characterized by brown pupae and tolerance to heat stress. In this strain, conditional female elimination is achieved simply by immersing eggs in warm water (34 °C), with pupal coloration serving as a visual quality-control measure. This inducible, early-acting female lethality enables stable colony amplification under normal conditions and allows cost-effective, efficient, and reliable mass production of male-only cohorts on demand. The system supports weekly production on the scale of billions of insects, with approximately 2,000 million sterile male flies produced per week, providing horticultural protection across thousands of square kilometers (Franz, 2005; Enkerlin et al., 2015; Bourtzis & Vreysen, 2021)

Despite the success of this temperature-based, high-throughput genetic sexing system in the medfly, similar achievements have not been replicated in other species despite extensive efforts. This limitation arises primarily from the serendipitous and labor-intensive nature of isolating recessive mutations. Although physical (for example, irradiation) or chemical (for example, ethyl methanesulfonate) mutagenesis can increase mutation rates, isolation still requires establishing hundreds of iso-families (single-parent-derived lineages). These must be intercrossed over multiple generations and repeatedly screened to identify desirable phenotypes. Even after isolating a suitable mutation, successful translocation is not guaranteed to produce a fertile and competitive lineage (Mashatola et al., 2018). In many cases,

the genetic basis of the phenotype remains unknown even when a stable line is obtained (Augustinos et al., 2022). Consequently, reproducing similar phenotypic traits in other species, even closely related ones, requires restarting the process from the beginning, with no certainty of success.

In mosquitoes, a stable loss-of-function GSS has been developed only for *Ae. aegypti*, based on a red-eye mutation. This naturally occurring recessive mutation, whose genetic basis remains to be fully characterized, prevents the darkening of the compound eye, an organ that first becomes visible at the pupal stage (Koskinioti et al., 2021). A successful translocation of the wild-type allele(s) to male-specific loci in this strain made the red-eye phenotype a female-exclusive trait. However, this late-emerging visual marker provides little advantage over current sexing approaches that are based on pupal size and morphology. Furthermore, the semi-sterility associated with the translocation may outweigh the benefits of using this strain compared to wild-type mosquitoes, limiting its practical utility.

Table1.1: Genetic sexing solution for *Aedes* mosquitoes

Technology	Selectable trait (Separation stage)	<i>Ae. aegypti</i>	<i>Ae. albopictus</i>	Notes
RIDL	Female specific repressable toxin (Pupae / adult)	Phuc et al., 2007	Labbé et al., 2012	Transgenic
Sex-specific marker	Testis-specific fluorescent marker (3rd instar)	Smith et al., 2007	N/A	Transgenic
Insecticide resistance	Male resistance to dieldrin (1st instar)	N/A	Lebon et al., 2018	Translocation
Loss-of function phenotype	Female eyes remains red (Late pupae)	Koskinioti et al., 2021	N/A	Translocation
Sex-specific marker	Sex-spliced fluorescent marker (1st instar)	Weng et al., 2023	N/A	Transgenic
Sex-linked marker	Sex-linked fluorescent marker (1st instar)	Lutrat et al., 2023; Compton et al., 2025	Lutrat et al., 2023	Non-transgenic output

Comparison of the various genetic sexing strains developed for *Aedes* mosquitoes classified by mode of action, type of genetic modification and reference for relevant publication for *Ae. aegypti* and *Ae. albopictus*.

1.8 The Sex Chromosomes

A key component in constructing GSSs is a reliable association between sex and phenotype. Traditionally, GSSs relied on random chromosomal translocations to link selectable markers with the Y chromosome or another sex-determining loci. This strategy was widely used because it required no prior knowledge of the organism's genetics, which is particularly relevant for sex chromosomes. Sex chromosomes are among the most difficult genomic regions to sequence and bioinformatically assemble (Carvalho et al., 2013; Nurk et al., 2022). Their non-recombining, heterochromatic, repeat-rich architecture defeats standard genome assembly methods and often yields incomplete, gap-filled assemblies.

A sex chromosome originates from an autosome that acquires a sex-determining gene (Bachtrog, 2013; Vicoso, 2019). The emergence of this gene introduces differential selective pressures between the homologous chromosomes. Alleles start to accumulate near the male-determining factor (M-factor), forming what becomes the M-locus, a proto-Y region enriched in male-beneficial and female-antagonistic genes (Charlesworth & Charlesworth, 2000; Olito & Abbott, 2025). Because maintaining a tight association between the sex-determining factor and these linked alleles preserves advantageous combinations, recombination between the two chromosomes becomes progressively suppressed (Ponnikas et al., 2018). This recombination arrest marks the onset of sex-chromosome differentiation. Once isolated from recombination, the proto-Y accumulates repetitive DNA, insertions and deleterious mutations that drive gene loss and structural decay (Bachtrog, 2013; Charlesworth and Charlesworth, 2000). The resulting reduction in gene content often favors the evolution of dosage-compensation mechanisms to restore balanced expression between sexes (Charlesworth & Charlesworth, 2000; Olito & Abbott, 2025). Although this general trajectory is conserved across taxa, Diptera display extraordinary variation in both the origin and fate of their sex chromosomes. Comparative genomic analyses across multiple fly families reveal frequent and independent turnovers, reversions to autosomal status, and recurrent recruitment of the same chromosomal element for sex linkage (Vicoso & Bachtrog, 2015; Bracewell & Bachtrog, 2020). In *Drosophila*, for example, the ancestral Y chromosome is no

longer required for sex determination but remains essential for male fertility, retaining a limited set of genes expressed exclusively during spermatogenesis (Zhang et al., 2020; Hafezi et al., 2024).

The primary triggers of sex determination in Diptera vary substantially among lineages. In *Drosophila*, sex is specified by the X-to-autosome ratio, which controls activation of the master regulator *Sex-lethal (Sxl)* during early embryogenesis (Bell et al., 1988; Salz et al., 1989). In contrast, other dipterans rely on dominant male-determining (M) factors located on Y chromosomes or autosomes. In tephritid fruit flies such as *Ceratitis capitata*, a small Y-linked gene called *MoY (Maleness-on-the-Y)* acts as the primary male determiner, being transiently expressed in early embryos to repress the female-promoting *transformer (Ctra)* autoregulatory loop (Meccariello et al., 2019). Similarly, in *Anopheles* mosquitoes, the gene *Yob* located on the Y chromosome functions as the M factor, initiating male development and causing female-specific lethality when misexpressed (Jiang et al., 2015; Krzywinska et al., 2016). These well-differentiated sex chromosomes have also evolved mechanisms of dosage compensation to balance X-linked gene expression between sexes (Mullon et al., 2015; Valsecchi et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2025). Ectopic transgenic expression of M factors outside their native chromosomal context has in several cases proven lethal or developmentally disruptive, as demonstrated for *Yob* in *Anopheles gambiae* (Krzywinska et al., 2016) and *MoY* in *Ceratitis capitata* (Meccariello et al., 2019). Dosage compensation has been postulated as a plausible explanation for this lethality, particularly in species with well-differentiated sex chromosomes, though the underlying mechanisms likely differ between species and remain incompletely understood.

Not all dipterans possess fully differentiated sex chromosomes. The house fly *Musca domestica* provides a notable exception, where the M factor gene *Mdmd* can reside on multiple chromosomes, resulting in populations with independent male-determining loci and frequent transitions between proto-Y chromosomes (Sharma et al., 2017; Son et al., 2019). In contrast, Culicine mosquitoes, which include *Aedes* spp., exhibit a more conserved sex-determination architecture. In these species, the M factor gene is autosomally located within a non-recombining region on chromosome 1. This gene encodes an RNA-binding protein that is both

necessary and sufficient for male development. Knockout of *nix* in genetic males results in complete feminization, whereas transgenic expression in genetic females induces full phenotypic masculinization - , including testis development and sperm production (Hall et al., 2015; Gomulski et al., 2018; Biedler et al., 2024). The limited size and homomorphic nature of the *Aedes* M-locus indicates that their sex chromosomes are in an evolutionary intermediate stage of differentiation. (Hall et al., 2015; Krzywinska et al., 2016). Notably, the autonomous function of *nix*, which can masculinize genetic females and produce fertile males independently of the M-locus context, coupled with the apparent absence of a dosage compensation mechanism may offer a unique engineering opportunity. These features could enable the development of novel genetic sexing strains (GSS) in *Aedes* *that* will circumvent the need of coherent M-locus assembly.

2. Scope and Aims of This Study

Mass production of female-free cohorts remains the major barrier to large-scale deployment of genetic control interventions against mosquitoes. This challenge can be addressed through the use of a genetic sexing strain (GSS). The limited availability of GSSs arises from the inherent unpredictability of their traditional development processes. The formation of a classical GSS depends on two stochastic steps: mutation isolation and genetic translocation, both of which rely heavily on chance. In contrast, the advent of precise genome editing technologies such as CRISPR/Cas9 has introduced a rational, engineering-based approach to generating *de novo* mutations through site-specific mutagenesis.

The historical development of the mediterranean fruit fly VIENNA 8 GSS highlights the inefficiency of traditional approaches. Establishing the strain required more than two decades, and elucidating the genetic basis of its *white pupae (wp)* selectable marker took an additional forty years (Rössler, 1979; Ward et al., 2021). Once the *wp* gene was identified, it was reintroduced *de novo* into several different pest species using CRISPR-mediated gene editing within a single year (Paulo et al., 2022). This comparison illustrates how CRISPR/Cas9 has transformed genetic engineering by streamlining site-directed genetic modification, accelerating the transformation and development of traits between organisms.

Building on the conceptual framework established by the VIENNA 8 strain, this study aims to harness such modern genome editing tools to develop a novel recessive mutation-based GSS for *Aedes albopictus*. The approach replaces random mutagenesis with targeted gene knockouts and substitutes random chromosomal translocation with site-specific integration. Unlike the classical forward-genetics paradigm, which begins with a phenotype and later infers its genetic basis, CRISPR-based genome editing allows a reverse-genetics strategy in which the function of preselected genes is interrogated through targeted disruption. This strategy, however, requires prior identification of candidate loci and accurate genomic information, both of which have historically been limited for *Ae. albopictus*.

In contrast, its close relative *Aedes aegypti* has long served as a genomic and experimental reference. It was the first mosquito species to be genetically

transformed (Morris et al., 1989), possesses a complete telomere-to-telomere genome assembly (Matthews et al., 2018), and was successfully edited using CRISPR within a year of the system's introduction (Doudna & Charpentier, 2014; Kistler et al., 2015). At the outset of this research, *Ae. albopictus* lacked an annotated genome assembly and established CRISPR protocols, underscoring the need for foundational work to enable rational, genome-based engineering in this species.

Aims of the Study

The overarching aim of this research is to establish a framework for the rational design of GSSs in *Ae. albopictus* using CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing. Specifically, this study seeks to:

1. **Identify candidate genes** whose disruption yields a visible, selectable, or otherwise distinguishable phenotype suitable for GSS development.
2. **Generate targeted loss-of-function alleles** through site-specific mutagenesis and confirm their phenotypic effects.
3. **Reintroduce a functional allele** into the mutant background in a sex-specific manner to form a genetic association between sex and phenotype.
4. **Characterize the resulting strain**, evaluating the obtained GSS phenotype stability, reliability and utility for large-scale application in mosquito control programs.

By leveraging modern CRISPR/Cas9-based genome editing, this research embraces a rational, scalable path to generating GSSs in non-model organisms. The resulting methodology holds broad potential for improving genetic control programs not only for *Ae. albopictus* but also for other species where traditional GSS development has been considered impractical.

3. Methodologies

3.1 Mosquito Strains, Handling, and Maintenance

3.1.1 Strain and rearing conditions

The FPA (Foshan) *Aedes albopictus* strain was used as the laboratory wild type in all experiments. Mosquitoes were maintained at $27 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity, and a 14:10 light:dark photoperiod. Unless stated otherwise, larvae were reared in $160 \times 135 \times 90$ mm plastic containers with 300 mL distilled water (DW) at a density of 0.667 larvae/mL. Rearing tanks received a daily supplement of fish food (Essence, Alltech-Coppens, Leende, NL). Pupae were collected every 48 hours and transferred to the designated cages using 100 mL sample cups. Adults were maintained in BugDorm 4M2222 cages (~ 14 L volume) with ad libitum access to a 10% sucrose solution supplemented with 0.1% methyl paraben. Females were fed thawed heparinized bovine blood spiked with 5 mg/mL adenosine 5'-triphosphate (ATP; Cayman Chemical, Ann Arbor, MI, USA) using a Hemotek feeding system (Discovery Workshops, Accrington, UK).

3.1.2 Egg collection, storage, and hatch

Four days after blood feeding, an oviposition cup (a 100 mL plastic cap with filter paper soaked in DW) was placed in the cage. After 24 hours, the paper was removed, placed in a 150 mm plastic closed Petri dish, air-dried for 24 hours, and sealed with Parafilm for storage at room temperature for up to 90 days. To synchronize hatch, eggs older than 96 hours were immersed for 6 hours in an oxygen-depleted hatching solution prepared by incubating 0.25 g nutrient broth and 0.05 g baker's yeast in 750 mL DW overnight at room temperature. L1 larvae were collected after 6 hours, or as L2 on the following day, then counted and distributed into rearing containers.

3.2 Nucleic Acid Extraction, Amplification, and Sequencing

3.2.1 DNA

Whole-body DNA was extracted with β -mercaptoethanol and the Zymo Quick-DNA Miniprep Kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, CA, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol. To exclude contamination and confirm sample sex, pooled and individual DNA libraries were amplified for the *nix* gene using OneTaq 2X Master Mix (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA, USA). Amplicons were verified by TBE-agarose gel electrophoresis. This PCR and gel electrophoresis workflow was used as the standard procedure for all genotyping and routine molecular screening throughout this study. SNP screening for laboratory population was performed using Sanger sequencing (Hy-Labs, Rehovot, Israel). For allele distribution analysis, Illumina amplicon sequencing was performed (Hy-Labs) with an average read depth of 100,000 reads per sample.

3.2.2 RNA

For transcriptomic analysis, whole-body RNA was extracted from 24–48 hour old adults in three biological replicates per group. Mosquitoes were anesthetized with CO₂ and pooled in groups of three into 2 mL tubes containing 2.3 mm zirconium–silicate beads and 300 μ L ice-cold TRI-Reagent (Zymo Research). Within 10 minutes of collection, samples were homogenized with a Minilys bead-beater (Bertin, Rockville, MD, USA) at 6,000 rpm for 30 seconds. The homogenate was mixed with an additional 800 μ L TRI-Reagent and incubated for 5 minutes at room temperature. Phase separation was induced by adding 220 μ L chloroform, vortexing 15 seconds, incubating 5 minutes, and centrifuging at 12,000 \times g for 15 minutes at 4 °C. The upper aqueous phase was transferred, mixed 1:1 with absolute ethanol, and loaded onto a Zymo-Spin IICR column. RNA was purified using the Zymo Direct-zol RNA Miniprep Kit according to the manufacturer's protocol.

For transcriptomics, mRNA was isolated by poly-A selection and libraries were prepared with the Illumina TruSeq Stranded mRNA Library Prep Kit. Sequencing was performed on a NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) using an S1

300-cycle kit with paired-end 2 × 150 bp reads, generating ~45 million read pairs per sample (G-INCPM, Weizmann Institute of Science, Rehovot, Israel).

3.3 Bioinformatics

3.3.1 Reference resources and software

Sequence analysis, including BLAST searches and primer design, was performed in Geneious Prime (Biomatters, Auckland, New Zealand) using NCBI resources. Analyses used the most recent *Ae. albopictus* assemblies available at the time: the canu_80X_arrow2.2 C6/36 cell-line assembly for initial steps, followed by Aalbo_primary.1, AalbF3, and AalbF5. Sex-specific whole-genome sequencing (WGS) libraries from Palatini et al. (2017) (NCBI BioProject PRJNA484104) and RNA-seq libraries from Gamez et al. (2020) (PRJNA563095) were used to support the investigation.

3.3.2 Ortholog analysis and target sequence identification

Amino acid sequences corresponding to the longest isoform of each candidate gene were retrieved from *Drosophila melanogaster* (FlyBase) and *Ae. aegypti* (VectorBase). These reference proteins were used as queries in *tblastn* searches against the *Ae. albopictus* genome assemblies. Candidate loci were evaluated based on sequence similarity (E-value and alignment coverage), gene structure conservation, synteny with neighboring genes, and RNA-seq expression profiles.

The combined evidence from these parameters was used to confirm orthology and to distinguish true orthologs from assembly artifacts or paralogous duplications. Genomic regions of interest were PCR-amplified and verified by Sanger sequencing to exclude assembly-induced duplications and to detect intraspecific sequence polymorphisms that could affect downstream analyses or guide RNA design.

3.3.3 CQ metric, coverage, and M-k-mer analysis

Preprocessing. Raw reads were trimmed with Trimmomatic v0.39 (LEADING:3 TRAILING:3 SLIDINGWINDOW:4:15 MINLEN:36).

CQ metric. Cleaned reads were aligned to the *Ae. albopictus* Aalbo_primary.1 coding sequences (NCBI RefSeq CF_006496715.1_cds_from_genomic.fna) using Bowtie v1.3.1 with exact matching and with all alignments reported (parameters: -v 0 -a). Alignments were sorted and deduplicated with SAMtools v1.12 to obtain unique counts per CDS for each sex. Library sizes were computed and counts were scaled to the average library size. Genes with fewer than 50 mapped male reads per 1 Kb of annotation were ignored. The CQ value was computed for each CDS as follows:

$$CQ = \frac{F_{norm} + 1}{M_{norm} + 1}$$

Where F_{norm} and M_{norm} are the normalized female and male counts.

Scaffold-level coverage. The same libraries were aligned to Aalbo_primary.1 with Bowtie (-v 0 -a). SAM files were converted to sorted BAM and indexed with SAMtools v1.12. Per-scaffold mapped reads were obtained with samtools idxstats. Per-base depth was computed with BEDTools v2.30.0 genomeCoverageBed -d.

Male-specific k-mers. Canonical 25-mers were counted from sex-specific WGS libraries and from the AalbF5 genome (GCF_035046485.1) using Jellyfish v2.3.0 (-C -m 25 -c 3 -s 1000000000). K-mer tables for male and female libraries were merged and normalized to average library size; only k-mers with male count > 0 were retained. Genomic 25-mers from AalbF5 were merged with normalized counts to produce a table of sequence, male and female counts, and genomic count. Male-unique k-mers were defined as those with male count > 30 and female count = 0. Male-unique k-mers were mapped to AalbF5 with Bowtie v1.3.1 (-v 0). BAM files were converted to BED with BEDTools, and coordinates were intersected with the AalbF5 annotation to identify genes overlapping male-unique k-mers.

3.3.4 Differential expression analysis

Adapters and poly-A/T stretches were removed with cutadapt (reads < 30 bp discarded). Clean reads were aligned to AalbF5 with STAR v2.7 (alignEndsType EndToEnd, outFilterMismatchNoverLmax = 0.04). PCR duplicates were removed with Picard MarkDuplicates (Broad Institute). Gene counts were obtained with htseq-count using the AalbF5 GTF. PCA was used for QC; outliers were defined a

priori as samples with PC1 or PC2 scores beyond 3 SD from the group mean. Differential expression was tested with DESeq2; genes with $|\log_2FC| > 2$ and $FDR < 0.05$ were considered differentially expressed. Genes were classified as specifically expressed if they were detected in all replicates of one group (raw count ≥ 1 in each replicate and cumulative count ≥ 5) and undetected in the other group.

3.4 Cloning, Mutagenesis, and Transgenesis

3.4.1 CRISPR/Cas9 sgRNA design and injection mixes

Potential CRISPR/Cas9 target sites were identified in the AalbF5 assembly. Target regions were PCR-amplified from a DNA pool of > 10 individuals and Sanger sequenced to generate consensus sequences and assess possible SNPs or polymorphisms. Consensus sequences were analyzed with CRISPOR (Concordet and Haeussler, 2018) to shortlist sgRNAs based on predicted specificity and efficiency.

For non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) mutagenesis, the injection mix contained 300 ng/ μ L SpCas9 protein and 80 ng/ μ L sgRNA (both from Integrated DNA Technologies, Coralville, IA, USA) preincubated as an RNP for 30 minutes at 37 °C. For homology-directed repair (HDR), the mix contained 300 ng/ μ L SpCas9, 40 ng/ μ L sgRNA, and 400 ng/ μ L donor plasmid.

3.4.2 Cloning

Constructs were designed with the NEBuilder Assembly Tool and assembled using the NEBuilder HiFi DNA Assembly Kit. PCRs used Q5 Hot Start High-Fidelity 2X Master Mix (all New England Biolabs). Plasmids were transformed into Mix & Go DH5 α competent *E. coli* (Zymo Research) and incubated overnight at 37 °C. Colony PCR screening used OneTaq 2X Master Mix with an extended initial denaturation of 1 minute at 94 °C. Positive colonies were processed with the Zyppy Plasmid Miniprep Kit and preserved as glycerol stocks for long-term storage at -80 °C. Plasmids were validated by restriction digestion and Sanger sequencing. For transposon-mediated transgenesis, validated plasmids were injected at 200 ng/ μ L

with 40 ng/μL of a mosquito codon-optimized *piggyBac* transposase helper plasmid (Lutrat et al., 2022).

3.4.3 Microinjection

Embryo microinjections followed Fuchs et al. (Fuchs et al., 2013). Four days after blood feeding, gravid mated females were transferred to vials lined with moist filter paper to induce oviposition. Freshly laid eggs (< 30 minutes old) were aligned on a PBS-wetted nitrocellulose membrane on a glass slide using a fine brush and partially covered with PBS-soaked blotting paper to maintain humidity. Quartz capillaries (inner diameter 0.7 mm, outer diameter 1.0 mm; Sutter Instrument, Novato, CA, USA) were pulled using Sutter's P-2000 puller (Settings: Heat= 750, Filament= 4, Velocity= 40, Delay= 150, Pull= 165). Injections were performed on an Olympus IX53 inverted microscope equipped with an MM-94 electric micromanipulator and MMO-4 hydraulic system (Narishige, Tokyo, Japan). A FemtoJet 4i (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) controlled delivery; air pressure was adjusted as needed to maintain stable flow and embryo viability.

Post-injection, slides were placed in a sealed humidified container and incubated at 27 °C for 48 hours without disturbance. The seal was then removed to permit gradual desiccation over 24 hours. Embryos were hatched using the solution in section 3.1.2. Emerged G0 with mosaic or transient phenotypes were reared and backcrossed to wild type. F2 intercross progeny displaying mutant phenotypes (Cas9 mutagenesis) or transgenic F1 individuals (*piggyBac* transgenesis) were selected to establish isofounder lines.

3.5 Mosquito experiments

3.5.1 Pupation dynamics

L1 larvae from two strains were counted 6 hours post-hatching and distributed into rearing trays as either single-strain cultures (monocultures) or mixed populations (co-reared, with equal numbers from each strain). Pupae were collected daily from the onset of pupation, sorted by strain based on cuticular coloration or transgenic

fluorescence, and by sex according to terminalia morphology, then assigned to the respective experimental groups.

3.5.2 Pupae imaging and analysis

Pupae collected 24 hours after pupation from co-reared trays were transferred to a 90 mm Petri dish filled to the brim with water. The dish was imaged under a Nikon D60 on a tripod using ambient LED illumination. Images were analyzed in Fiji (ImageJ v1.53). RGB channels were split; a binary mask was created from the blue channel; regions of interest (ROIs) were detected with Particle Analyzer (size: 1000–6000 pixels, circularity: 0.50–1.00). ROIs were applied to the red channel to measure mean red-channel intensity and size parameters (minor axis, major axis, diameter, area). Size measurements were normalized to the Petri dish diameter in the image.

3.5.3 High-density rearing and sexual bimaturism

For high-density rearing, three replicate trays per strain were seeded with 1,500 L1 larvae each in 500 mL water (3 larvae/mL) in trays with 325 × 175 mm surface area (2.6 larvae/cm²). Larvae were fed daily with TetraBits Complete (Tetra, Melle, Germany). Trays were monitored daily for pupation onset. Over five days following the first pupation event, pupae were collected at ten time points, sexed by terminalia morphology, and counted. Recovery rates were calculated as pupae collected divided by initial larval count per tray. Protandry levels was quantified using the Sexual Bimaturism index (Blanckenhorn et al., 2007):

$$SBM = \frac{2(F-M)}{F+M}$$

where F and M are the mean pupation times (days) for females and males, respectively.

3.5.4 Mating Competitiveness

Co-reared wild-type and transheterozygous GSS pupae were collected on the same day, sexed, and separated. Four days after adult emergence, males were counted and transferred to a competition cage using an electric aspirator (BioQuip, Rancho

Dominguez, CA, USA). The male number and the transgenic:wild-type ratio varied by experiment. One hour later, once males had dispersed from the collection vessel, four-day-old virgin females were introduced in numbers equal to the smaller male group. The following day, a blood meal was provided. F1 offspring were screened for the transgenic marker to estimate the proportion sired by transgenic males.

Competitiveness (C) was calculated using a modified Fried's Index calculation, adapted from sterility to transgenic mosquitoes for this study:

$$C = \frac{(Ha-E)/(E-Hs)}{R} \rightarrow \frac{(1-E)/(E-(1-Tr))}{R} \Rightarrow \frac{(1-E)}{R \cdot (E-(1-Tr))}$$

where 1 represents the proportion of non-transgenic offspring from wild-type males (replacing the Ha originally used for indicating natural fertility of females in the original equation), E is the observed proportion of non-transgenic offspring in the competition cage, Tr is the proportion of transgenic offspring sired by transgenic males (replacing Hs originally denotes the residual fertility of the sterile males), and R is the ratio of transgenic to wild-type males.

3.5.5 Female Refractoriness

Two reciprocal mating assays tested whether transgenic males induce post-mating female refractoriness. In the bulk-mating assay, fifty unmated five-day-old females were introduced into a cage containing either twenty-five GSS males (OpIE2:eGFP) or twenty-five regular males carrying OpIE2:dsRED. After two hours, females were blood-fed and transferred to a cage containing twenty-five males of the opposite type. Four days later, three oviposition bowls per cage were collected, and L₂ larvae were screened under GFP and dsRED filters to determine paternity. In the second, single-female mating assay, twenty-five females were introduced individually into cages containing either twenty-five GSS (OpIE2:eGFP) or twenty-five regular (OpIE2:dsRED) males. Each female was observed for pair formation and copulation. After at least one copulation lasting ≥ 20 seconds, the female was transferred to a cage with twenty-five males of the opposite type. Cages were blood-fed the same day. Four days later, females were isolated for oviposition, and single-female clutches from twenty females per group were scored by larval fluorescence.

3.6 Modeling Competitiveness using Mating Simulator

An R simulation estimated the expected proportion of transgenic F1 offspring under pre- and post-mating competitiveness. The simulated population consisted of 25 females, with transgenic male release rates $P \in \{0.3333, 0.5, 0.6667, 0.8333\}$ and competitiveness coefficients $C \in \{0.01, 0.25, 0.5, 1.0\}$. Each female received a clutch size drawn from a Poisson distribution with $\lambda \in \{33, 44, 55\}$ eggs and two mating partners (P1, P2). The identity of each mate (transgenic or wild type) was assigned by the following mating probability:

$$X = \frac{C \times P}{1 - P + C \times P}$$

Where X represents the probability of a female mating with a transgenic male, C is the transgenic male competitiveness coefficient, and P is the relative proportion of transgenic males in the population.

The simulation was run for 1,000 iterations for each parameter combination, generating a complete mating log assigning every female her clutch size and mating partners identities (P1, P2). These parameters were then used to calculate the proportion of transgenic offspring produced by each female under three behavioral models:

1. **Monogamous:** offspring identity was determined by P1; transgenic P1 contributed 50% transgenic offspring per clutch.
2. **Polygamous:** if P1 and P2 identities differed, the proportion of transgenic offspring was scaled by a post-mating competitiveness factor $PMC \in \{1.0, 0.5, 0.25, 0.1\}$.
3. **Reluctant:** females rejected transgenic P1 but accepted wild-type P1; transgenic offspring were produced only when both P1 and P2 were transgenic.

An excerpt from the simulated mating log (left) and the corresponding calculation of transgenic progeny under the different models (right) are shown below:

♀ ID	Clutch	P ₁	P ₂	Mono	Poly100	Poly50	Poly25	Poly10	Reluctant
25530	52	WT	WT	0	0	0	0	0	0
25531	46	WT	Trans	0	12	8	5	0	0
25532	50	Trans	WT	25	12	8	5	0	0
25533	32	Trans	Trans	16	16	16	16	16	16
25534	44	WT	Trans	0	11	7	4	0	0
25535	49	WT	WT	0	0	0	0	0	0

Simulated mean transgenic proportions for each model were compared with experimental data from competition-cage assays. A linear regression model was fitted to predict observed transgenic proportions as a function of release rate. Model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), adjusted R², and corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), identifying the best-fitting combination of competitiveness, female mating behavior, and post-mating competitiveness parameters.

3.7 Data Analysis and Statistics

All statistical analyses were performed in R v4.4.1. Normality was assessed with the Shapiro–Wilk test and homogeneity of variance with Levene’s test. For normally distributed data, group comparisons used one-way ANOVA or ANCOVA where appropriate, with Tukey’s HSD for post hoc testing. Two-group comparisons used unpaired or paired t-tests as appropriate. Non-normal data were analyzed with the Kruskal–Wallis test followed by Dunn’s post hoc test. Phenotype proportions were compared with chi-square tests and binomial generalized linear models. Statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. Plots were generated with ggplot2 and networkD3.

3.7 Data availability

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Chapter I - Engineering a Selectable Trait

4.1 Introduction

Genetic sexing strains (GSS) are engineered pest strains that express a selectable trait in a sex-specific manner. One approach for developing GSS relies on a recessive loss-of-function mutation, in which females homozygous for the mutation exhibit the selectable phenotype, while males retain the wild-type phenotype through a translocated functional allele to the sex-chromosome. This configuration enables reliable sex separation during rearing for release operations (Franz et al., 2021). Depending on the trait, such modification may allow early sex separation, improve the accuracy and efficiency of sorting, or permit automated elimination of one sex at early developmental stages (Papathanos et al., 2018). The identification of a suitable selectable phenotype is therefore a critical first step in GSS development.

Historically, the identification of suitable selectable traits was accomplished through a forward-genetic approach that did not require prior genetic data. In this method, random mutagenesis was used to generate genetic variation, and novel phenotypes were identified through systematic crossing and screening. Although this strategy was flexible and widely applied, only a small number of stable and practical mutations were ultimately obtained across insect species (Bellen et al., 2004; Chen et al., 2022). Recent advances in genomics have since identified the genetic basis of several of these classical mutations (Ward et al., 2021; Aumann et al., 2025).

The development of modern molecular tools has transformed functional genetics by enabling targeted, reverse-genetic approaches. The CRISPR-Cas9 system in particular, provides a precise method for generating specific knockouts to study gene function (Doudna & Charpentier, 2014). This system employs a programmable endonuclease to introduce targeted DNA cleavage at defined genomic loci. A synthetic single-guide RNA (sgRNA), complementary to the selected target sequence, directs the Cas9 enzyme to create a double-stranded break (DSB) at that site. The DSB is then repaired by error-prone mechanisms such as non-homologous end joining, which frequently resolves with insertions or deletions within the targeted region. When the disrupted site lies within a coding sequence, these alterations can

shift the reading frame or affect essential motifs, producing loss-of-function alleles (Li et al., 2017). Although this approach requires prior knowledge of the target sequence, it substantially reduces the need for extensive phenotypic screening and is particularly advantageous for non-model organisms which have complex rearing requirements, relatively long generation times, and moderate fecundity (Hsu et al., 2014).

Building on previous studies that characterized visible phenotypes and identified their genetic basis in dipteran models such as *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Aedes aegypti* (Bellen et al., 2004; Kistler et al., 2015; Li et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2022), this work applied those insights to identify orthologs in *Aedes albopictus* expected to produce comparable loss-of-function traits. The selection of a gene suitable for GSS development was guided by five principal criteria:

1. **Single-copy:** The gene should be single copy, lacking functional paralogs that can rescue gene function, ensuring that its disruption produces a clear and interpretable phenotype without requiring multiple knockouts.
2. **Fully recessive:** The mutation must be completely recessive and impose no fitness costs on heterozygotes. This property preserves the field competitiveness of males intended for release.
3. **Homozygous viable:** The gene should not be essential for any developmental or physiological processes, allowing homozygous mutants to remain viable while displaying the selectable phenotype. This feature enables the stable maintenance of homozygous colonies in laboratory conditions.
4. **Early effect:** The phenotype should be detectable and selectable from early larval or even embryonic stages to allow early sex discrimination or selection. This ensures that no resources are wasted to rear females.
5. **Simple structure:** The gene should have a simple exon–intron organization and a minimal number of transcriptional isoforms. Alternative splicing can hinder complete knockout if the targeted exon is skipped in some transcripts,

and it can complicate downstream rescue design by requiring restoration of all functional variants.

Development of a GSS necessitates retaining gene function in one sex; therefore, the successful design of a functional rescue construct represents a critical complementary step. The rescue construct must restore gene activity and include the complete coding sequence along with essential cis-regulatory regions to reproduce the endogenous expression pattern. Successful rescue therefore depends on the accurate inclusion of regulatory elements and integration within a genomic context that preserves normal expression (Nolan & Hammond, 2022).

This chapter describes the selection, generation, and functional rescue of a loss-of-function mutation in *Ae. albopictus*, establishing a framework for developing selectable phenotypes that can be incorporated into future GSSs.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 Target selection

Over the past century, the genetic basis of numerous mutations in *Drosophila* has been elucidated (Chyb & Gompel, 2013). From these studies, a catalog of visible phenotypes and their corresponding genetic determinants was compiled. To identify orthologs of these genes in the most recent *Ae. albopictus* genome assembly, tBLASTn searches were performed to curate a list of potential targets [Table 4.1]. The identified orthologs were classified as 1:1 or 1:many, manually annotated to verify the accuracy of gene models, and ranked according to their expected phenotype, including the developmental stage at which the phenotype would be selectable. These phenotypes include eye color and morphology phenotypes such as *white* (LOC109397595), *cardinal* (LOC115269315), and *glass* (LOC109429302). These mutations manifest relatively late, becoming visible at the pupal stage; they may serve as useful secondary markers for pupal sexing. However, their complex gene structures, typically consisting of five or six exons with multiple isoforms, make them less suitable for straightforward knockout and rescue [Table 4.1]. Wing-related phenotypes such as *curled* (LOC109398703) and *wingless* (LOC109621322) are only evident in adults. Although these traits are unsuitable for early sexing, the

flightless phenotype associated with them could, in principle, eliminate the need for sex separation by preventing female flight. However, such severe fitness costs would likely prevent sustainable colony maintenance. Body color mutations such as *ebony* (LOC109430448) and *yellow* (LOC109402083) are well-studied evolutionarily conserved genes and can be scored from early developmental stages. The *ebony* gene, however, consists of seven exons, making it structurally more complex than *yellow*, which contains only two. Additionally, the dark cuticle phenotype associated with *ebony* is difficult to distinguish in the naturally dark *Ae. albopictus*.

Table 4.1: Ortholog status in *Aedes* for *Drosophila melanogaster* loss-of-function mutation

<i>D. melanogaster</i>			<i>Aedes spp.</i>			
Name	Phenotype	Fitness	Scorable stage	Orthologs	# of exons	Reproduced?
WT		-	-	-	-	-
<i>cardinal</i>		No	Pupa	3	5	Chen et al., 2022
<i>curled</i>		Flightless	Adult	2	6	No
<i>glass</i>		No	Pupa	2	6	No
<i>ebony</i>		No	Larva	2	7	Li et al., 2017 Nikolouli et al., 2025*
<i>yellow</i>		No	Larva	1	2	Li et al., 2017* Liu et al., 2019†
<i>white</i>		Blindness	Pupa	2	5	M. Li et al., 2017*
<i>wingless</i>		Flightless	Adult	1	5	No

List of recessive, visually scorable loss-of-function mutations described in the model organism *Drosophila melanogaster* (left), and their putative orthologs in *Aedes albopictus* genome assembly (right). The phenotype earliest scorable stage, copy number and CDS exon complexity are indicated. Previously documented successful reproduction of the phenotype in *Aedes* is specified, using an asterisk* for *Aedes aegypti* and dagger † for *Ae. albopictus*.

In contrast, disruption of *yellow* results in a pronounced loss of cuticle pigmentation that is easily detected at early stages. This phenotype has been successfully

reproduced in *Ae. aegypti* (Li et al., 2017) and *Ae. albopictus* (Liu et al., 2019) using CRISPR-Cas9 without reported fitness costs. Based on these features, yellow was selected as the most promising candidate, notably for its simple two-exon structure that produces a single mRNA isoform. A single-guide RNA (sgRNA) targeting the first exon of the coding sequence was designed to disrupt *yellow* function and generate a visible, loss-of-function phenotype.

4.2.2 Generation of *yellow* mutant strain

A *yellow* mutation was generated by microinjection of CRISPR-Cas9 ribonucleoprotein (RNP) complexes into syncytial embryos. The complexes consisted of sgRNA134 and Cas9 protein targeting the coding sequence located 134 base pairs downstream of the start codon. Mosaic pigmentation was frequently observed among surviving G₀ individuals [Fig. 4.1]. Eleven mosaics were backcrossed to wild-type (WT) mosquitoes to establish isofamilies, of which seven produced viable F₁ progeny.

Fig. 4.1 G₀ mosaicism for the yellow mutation.

Surviving individuals microinjected at the egg stage with preactivated Cas9 and sgRNA134 exhibit mosaic cuticle pigmentation. Panels show: **A)** mosaic pupae, **B)** mosaic male adults, and **C)** mosaic female adults. Individuals displaying mosaicism are marked with arrows and photographed alongside uninjected wild-type controls of the same age and sex.

Intercrossing within these seven lineages resulted in F₂ individuals displaying the *yellow* phenotype in four of them. A stable *yellow* strain was subsequently established by crossing males and females originating from two distinct isofamilies. Amplicon sequencing of pooled individuals from this strain revealed four independent null alleles, each containing frameshift mutations that introduced premature stop

codons upstream of the *yellow* Major Royal Jelly Protein (MRJP) domain and resulting in the loss of AlphaFold predicted tertiary structure of Yellow [Fig. 4.2].

Figure. 4.2 Characterization of the *yellow* mutant phenotype.

A) Structure of the *yellow* gene showing the location of the sgRNA¹³⁴ target in the first exon, the Major Royal Jelly Protein (MJRP) domain and the stop codon (TAG). The target site of sgRNA¹³⁴ (red) and PAM site (blue) is shown followed by AlphaFold2-predicted 3D structure of Yellow. **B)** CRISPR-induced *yellow* mutant alleles isolated. Alignment view of mutant alleles containing deletions or insertions causing frameshifts and premature termination. All alleles encode proteins lacking the MJRP motif and correct tertiary structure structure.

4.2.3 Characterizing the *yellow* phenotype

In insects, melanin synthesis produces multiple pigments by converting tyrosine into reactive quinone intermediates through sequential oxidation steps. The *yellow* (*y*) gene catalyzes the formation and deposition of the dark pigment dopamine-melanin. Although its precise function remains unresolved, empirical studies have demonstrated its key role in cuticular tanning (Futahashi et al., 2022). Loss of *yellow* function in *Ae. albopictus* produced mutants that failed to darken properly after ecdysis, resulting in a distinct pale phenotype across developmental stages [Fig. 4.3]. Reduced melanization was evident in larvae, particularly in the antennae, mental plates, lateral hairs, tracheae, siphons, and saddles [Fig. 4.3A–B]. In pupae, pigmentation loss was most pronounced in the dorsal mesothorax and tergum [Fig. 4.3C]. Adult *Ae. albopictus* exhibited yellow rather than black-and-white “tiger stripes” [Fig. 4.3D]. Eggs laid by *yellow* females failed to fully melanize, remaining golden-brown instead of black as in WT eggs [Fig. 4.3E]

Figure 4.2 *yellow* loss of function results in a vivid phenotype throughout ontogeny.

A-E) Comparison of *WT* and *yellow* phenotype across development indicating pigmentation differences in key structures with arrows: **A,B)** Fourth instar larvae - trachea (Tr), syphon (Sy), saddle (Sa), lateral hairs (LH), mental plate (MP), and antenna (An). **C)** One-day-old male pupae - tergum (Te) and mesothorax (M). **D)** Adult females. **E)** One-day-old eggs laid by *WT* and *yellow* females.

consistent with previous reports in other *yellow* family members (Noh et al., 2020). The egg-melanization phenotype was maternally determined and persisted when *yellow* females were crossed with WT males. The disruption of *yellow* has been shown to cause a range of phenotypic effects extending beyond melanization in various insects. Studies in *Spodoptera litura* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) *yellow* larvae developed deformed body segmentation and abnormal molting (Liu et al., 2020). In honeybees, *yellow* influences brain monoamine levels and behavior (Buttstedt et al., 2014); and in *Drosophila melanogaster* *yellow* affects the sex-comb morphology, a male-specific courtship structure (Massey et al., 2019). Such pleiotropic effects necessitate careful evaluation of potential fitness impacts, as these may compromise the utility of *yellow* mutants in mass rearing and genetic control programs (Massey & Wittkopp, 2016). Although previously reported *Aedes yellow* mutants did not exhibit apparent fitness costs (Li et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2019), quantitative assessments were not conducted. Because variation in target sites and strain backgrounds can influence phenotypic outcomes, an evaluation of potential fitness effects was therefore performed. Three traits associated with overall fitness were examined: development time, body size, and egg hatch rate. To minimize technical variation, *yellow* and WT mosquitoes used in these experiments were hatched simultaneously and co-reared as larvae in the same containers to ensure identical conditions of age, food availability, and density throughout the experiment. Five co-rearing trays were analyzed, and single-strain trays (three for each strain) served as controls .

4.2.3.1 Development time

First-instar larvae from both strains were counted immediately after hatching and transferred to rearing trays at a fixed density of 200 larvae per tray. Larvae were monitored daily for pupation. The first pupae (19 in total) were observed five days after hatching, and pupation peaked on day seven with 534 pupae. By day nine, 95% of pupae had been collected. Pupae collection continued for one week following the onset of pupation, and the sex and phenotype of each individual were recorded. A total of 826 pupae (82.6% recovery) were obtained from co-reared trays, slightly higher than from single-strain WT trays (479 pupae, 80.8%) and *yellow* trays (485 pupae, 79.8%). Pupation dynamics did not differ between the single-strain WT and

yellow larvae, with a median pupation day of seven for males and eight for females. In contrast, co-reared males of both strains developed faster, with a median pupation day of six, while female pupation time remained consistent across treatments [Fig. 4.3A]. A significant difference in pupation time was detected between co-reared WT and *yellow* females (7.62 ± 0.09 vs. 8.00 ± 0.12 days, Wilcoxon ranked-sum test, $W = 16633$, $p < 0.001$) [Fig. 4.3B].

Figure 4.3: Comparison of Pupation Dynamics Between WT and *yellow* strain.

Daily recording of pupation events of larvae of the WT (grey) or *yellow* (yellow) strain according to sex - males (blue upper tiles) and female (pink bottom tiles) **A)** Population pyramids displaying the age (in days, from egg hatch) of pupation events of larvae reared as single strain or co-reared in a container with mixed population. Dashed red line indicate median age of pupation for each group. **B)** Mean age of pupation (days, from hatch) of the aforementioned groups, significant differences indicated by asterisks (Wilcoxon; $p < 0.05$).

4.2.3.2 Body size

Morphometric measurements were obtained from 1,096 imaged pupae. However, the assumption of homogeneity of variance was violated in this dataset (Levene's test, $p < 0.05$), preventing a reliable assessment of the rearing condition effect on

size (single vs. co-reared). Therefore, subsequent analyses were restricted to co-reared pupae ($n = 482$). Despite a pronounced difference in hue between WT and yellow pupae (34.48%), no significant size differences were detected between males of the two strains. Similarly, key morphometric parameters, including pupal width and cephalothorax perimeter, did not differ significantly between WT and yellow females [Fig. 4.3]. Yellow females exhibited slightly larger mean area (+3.23%), major axis length (+3.84%), and Feret diameter (+3.41%) compared with WT females; overall the effect size of these differences was small.

Figure 4.3: Color and size differences between WT and yellow.

Measurements are shown for males (upper, blue tiles) and females (lower, pink tiles), including: **A**) pupal pigmentation intensity (mean gray value), **B**) pupal width (mm), and **C**) cephalothorax perimeter. significant differences indicated by asterisks (Wilcoxon; $p < 0.05$).

4.2.3.3 Egg desiccation tolerance

During routine maintenance of the *yellow* line, fluctuations in egg hatching rate were observed. Previous studies have indicated that members of the *yellow*-family genes contribute to eggshell melanization, thereby enhancing hardening and desiccation resistance in *Ae. albopictus* (Noh et al., 2020, 2021). Given the golden-brown coloration of *yellow* eggs [Fig. 4.2E], it was hypothesized that the absence of maternal *yellow* function may compromise desiccation resistance and embryonic dormancy, traits that are essential for long-distance dispersal (Girard et al., 2024; Swan et al., 2022).

To test this hypothesis, twelve egg batches were collected from crosses involving *yellow* males with WT and *yellow* females, and the numbers of dark (WT) and yellow

eggs were recorded. Every seven days, three egg batches were randomly selected for hatching and larvae were screened for cuticle color to calculate relative hatching rates. *Yellow* eggs exhibited significantly lower hatching rates than WT eggs at all time points (paired t-test, $t(11) = 10.06$, $p < 0.001$; ANCOVA, phenotype: $F(1,18) = 10.97$, $p = 0.0039$; storage duration: $F(1,18) = 9.71$, $p = 0.0060$; Tukey–Kramer HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). WT egg viability remained above 50% until the end of the experiment and declined only after the third week, whereas *yellow* eggs became nonviable by the fourth week [Fig. 4.4A]. In desiccation assays, four-day-old *yellow* and WT eggs were transferred from moist filter papers to glass slides and observed under a microscope during drying. Within minutes, most *yellow* eggs displayed visible signs of desiccation, including irreversible chorionic collapse and complete loss of viability, whereas WT eggs retained structural integrity [Fig. 4.4B].

Figure 4.4: Storage and desiccation tolerance of WT and *yellow* eggs.

A) Hatching rates of stored WT and *yellow* eggs tracked over one month. Hatching rates were calculated as the proportion of eggs that successfully developed into L2 larvae. Error bars denote standard error. Statistical significance was determined by ANCOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey-Kramer HSD, with significant differences indicated by letter groups ($\alpha = 0.05$). **B)** Time-lapse images of mature, 4-day-old eggs WT and *yellow* eggs mounted on a glass slide and photographed 1- and 6-minutes following removal from moist oviposition egg papers.

These results indicate that *yellow* strain eggs exhibit acute intolerance to desiccation. However, aside from this trait, no other post-hatching fitness costs, such as differences in body size or excess mortality, were detected. Following adjustments

to egg handling, including increased moisture in egg containers, and storage duration, limiting dry storage to a maximum of two weeks, the yellow line established in this study has been stably maintained for more than 30 generations.

4.2.4 Generation and testing of *yellow* transgenic rescues

To restore the pigmented phenotype, a minimal *yellow* (mini-*yellow*) rescue construct, EnYR, was designed. The construct consisted of the *yellow* coding sequence (CDS) excluding its large 25-kbp intron, combined with 1.1 kbp of upstream regulatory sequence and 660 bp of the presumed terminator region, all cloned in-frame. EnYR was inserted into a *piggyBac* transformation vector containing an eGFP marker driven by the OpIE2 promoter [Fig. 4.5A]. Because the extent and activity of the native regulatory elements were uncertain, a second construct, HspYR, was generated in which mini-*yellow* expression was driven by the constitutive *hsp83* promoter. This promoter, selected for its strong transcriptomic activity (Gamez et al., 2020; Webster & Scott, 2021).

The fragility of *yellow* eggs, consistent with their desiccation susceptibility, prevented successful direct microinjection, as no embryos survived the procedure. Consequently, both constructs were injected into WT embryos, and the transgenes were subsequently introduced into the *yellow* background through introgression. Three independent transgenic lines were established for each construct (EnYR and HspYR). Transgenic males from each of the six isofamilies were crossed with *yellow* females for two generations [Fig. 4.5B]. In the F₂ generation, the frequency of the *yellow* phenotype and its co-occurrence with the eGFP marker were analyzed to assess genetic rescue. In EnYR crosses, both yellow and dark progeny were eGFP-positive, and phenotype frequencies were comparable to control crosses involving non-transgenic F₁ males, indicating that EnYR did not restore pigmentation [Fig. 4.5C]. In contrast, HspYR fully rescued pigmentation, with all transgenic individuals displaying WT-like dark coloration [Fig. 4.5C]. The proportion of dark F₂ individuals increased to 81.78 ± 1.24%, confirming successful rescue across all HspYR lines. The rescue also restored egg desiccation tolerance, and allowed the long-term maintenance of the *yellow* strain through mating of yellow males with transgenic HspYR females.

Figure 4.5: Transgenic mini-yellow restores mosquito pigmentation.

A) Structure of EnYR and HspYR rescue constructs containing the mini-yellow coding sequence (CDS) driven either by endogenous yellow regulatory elements or the *hsp83* promoter and p10 terminator. Both constructs also contain the OpIE2:eGFP transformation marker and piggyBac arms. **B)** Crossing scheme to test complementation. Transgenic males homozygous for the native yellow (y^+) allele were crossed to homozygous yellow (y^-) mutant females, producing F1 progeny heterozygous at the yellow (y^+/y^-) locus and carrying the mini-yellow rescue construct. F1 transgenic males were then test-crossed with homozygous yellow (y^-) mutant females to evaluate pigmentation restoration in F2 progeny. As a control non-transgenic F1 heterozygous males were crossed to homozygous y^- females. **C)** Distribution of pigmentation phenotypes for dark and yellow among transgenic and non-transgenic individuals. Significant reduction from a default 50% yellow (Z-test, $p < 0.05$) is indicated.

These results indicate that the regulatory regions selected for EnYR were insufficient to drive mini-yellow expression, whereas the *hsp83* promoter provided strong, constitutive expression that effectively complemented the yellow loss-of-function phenotype.

4.3 Discussion

A fundamental requirement for GSS is the establishment of a selectable trait that enables rapid discrimination and separation of individuals carrying the trait from those that do not. With the aim of rendering this trait sex-specific thereby enabling efficient sex sorting. In here the use of conserved and previously characterized *yellow* mutation was investigated as a stable and easily scorable phenotypic marker. The gene was identified through ortholog analysis and disrupted in *Ae. albopictus* using CRISPR-Cas9-mediated site-specific mutagenesis within a reverse-genetic framework. Beyond melanization, this study identified significant effects not previously reported in *Aedes yellow* mutants (Li *et al.*, 2017; Liu *et al.*, 2019). These differences may stem from the specific allele generated by the mutation, variation in the genetic background of the laboratory strains, or prior oversight. The most prominent one was the reduced hatching rate of *yellow* eggs, likely due to increased desiccation sensitivity resulting from impaired chorion melanization. This phenotype is consistent with previously reported *Ae. aegypti* eggs desiccation sensitivity associated with impaired chorion melanization (Noh *et al.*, 2020). Comparable observations have been documented in other mosquitoes where reduced eggshell melanization lowers embryonic survival under dry conditions (Farnesi *et al.*, 2017); in *Bombyx mori*, mutations in melanin-synthesis genes result in pale eggs with low hatch rates (Luo *et al.*, 2021); and in *Tribolium castaneum*, non-melanized eggs are more susceptible to environmental stress (Jacobs *et al.*, 2017). These parallels highlight the conserved role of melanization in egg protection. Importantly, In *Ae. albopictus*, which relies on desiccation-resistant eggs for storage and colony expansion, this defect could compromise strain maintenance.

A slight delay in pupation among *yellow* females co-reared with WT larvae suggests a mild competitive fitness cost, possibly due to males outcompeting females for nutritional resources and completing development earlier. Morphometric analyses revealed no significant size-related differences, although co-reared *yellow* females exhibited slightly larger body metrics. This pattern may reflect relaxed competition following early male pupation, consistent with the negative correlation between larval density and body size (Esperk *et al.*, 2007), or minor differences in pupal age near

emergence (Koenraadt, 2008). The absence of measurable size-related costs supports the suitability of the *yellow* mutation for routine rearing and GSS development.

The rescue experiments, designed to restore yellow gene function in the mutant background, provided an interesting case study. The EnYR construct, comprising the concatenated yellow coding sequence driven by its native upstream region, failed to recover the normal phenotype. This suggests that promoter activity within the 1.1-kb fragment was insufficient, or that key regulatory elements located within the intron were missing (Nolan & Hammond, 2022). Alternatively, the absence of intron and pre-mRNA splicing may have prevented upregulation of yellow expression through intron-mediated enhancement, a mechanism by which splicing increases transcript abundance and protein yield (Kowal et al., 2025). In contrast, the HspYR construct, under the *hsp83* promoter, fully restored pigmentation and egg desiccation tolerance, implying that strong constitutive expression is necessary for full rescue.

Together, the yellow mutation and its successful rescue establish a strong foundation for developing GSSs in *Ae. albopictus*. The mutation's distinct, easily scorable phenotype, visible during larval and pupal stages, can benefit both manual and automated sex sorting. Achieving female-specific disruption of yellow represents the next step toward enhancing genetic control interventions (Rendón et al., 2004). This could be achieved through sex-specific promoters, differential splicing, or M-locus integration of the rescue construct. The desiccation-sensitive egg phenotype, though disadvantageous for long-term storage, may be mitigated through optimized wet-storage protocols (Zheng et al., 2015), and could even serve as a biosafety feature by preventing survival of accidentally released females in incompatible insect technique (IIT) programs.

The pleiotropic effects of yellow emphasize the importance of thorough fitness evaluations following its loss of function. The establishment of a stable yellow mutant line and its successful rescue provide a solid foundation for developing a color-based sexing system. Efforts to render this rescue male specific are described in the following chapter, marking the next step toward the development of a reliable, efficient, and robust sexing solution.

Chapter II - Male specific recovery

5.1 - Introduction

Following the successful generation and rescue of the yellow phenotype described in the previous chapter, this chapter aims to make the rescue construct sex-specific, advancing the development of a genetic sexing strain (GSS) in *Aedes albopictus*. One approach to achieving this male-exclusive linkage is through physical integration of the rescue construct into a sex chromosome.

In most organisms, sex is genetically determined by heteromorphic chromosomes, where one sex carries homologous pairs (e.g., XX females) and the other a heterologous pair (XY males). These sex chromosomes evolved from ordinary autosomes following the emergence of sex-determining genes, such as the mammalian SRY, avian HINTW, or fish dmy (Bachtrog et al., 2014). Over time, auxiliary genes accumulated around these loci to reinforce the primary determinant and suppress traits of the opposite sex (Klein et al., 2021). To preserve linkage between the sex-determining factor and its associated genes, recombination is suppressed in the surrounding region. The loss of recombination prevents the removal of accumulated duplications and transposable elements, leading to heterochromatinization, extensive deletions, and gene loss. This progressive gene loss necessitated the evolution of dosage compensation mechanisms to maintain balanced expression between the sexes, independent of karyotype (Vicoso, 2019). This process results in the stereotypical XY system, in which the highly heterochromatic sex chromosomes are cytologically distinguishable by their reduced size.

Despite their relatively small size, sex chromosomes remain among the most challenging genomic regions to assemble due to their high repeat content and palindromic structure. As a result, they are often misrepresented or fragmented into numerous short, unmapped scaffolds in genome assemblies (Carvalho et al., 2013). To overcome these challenges, coverage-based comparative approaches have been developed to identify sex-chromosome-derived sequences. By exploiting differences in copy number between male and female genomes, these methods identify

sex-linked scaffolds without requiring contiguous chromosome assemblies (Muyle et al., 2016; Carvalho et al., 2013). Similarly, the chromosome quotient (CQ) method and k-mer comparison which leverage sex-specific reads or differences in male-to-female mapped read ratios, respectively, have been successfully applied to detect Y-derived genes in *Drosophila*, humans, and *Anopheles* mosquitoes (Hall et al., 2013; Jiang et al., 2014; Hall et al., 2016; Papathanos & Windbichler, 2018).

Mosquitoes of the Culicinae subfamily, including *Aedes* and *Culex*, lack cytologically distinct sex chromosomes. Both sexes possess a homomorphic karyotype, and sex is determined by a dominant male-determining locus (M-locus) on chromosome 1. In *Aedes*, the M-locus contains *nix*, a male-determining gene encoding an RNA-binding protein with two RNA-recognition motifs (Hall et al., 2015; Krzywinska et al., 2016). *nix* acts as an upstream regulator of sex-specific splicing of *doublesex* (*dsx*) and *fruitless* (*fru*), promoting male differentiation (Aryan et al., 2020). Comparative analyses have revealed that *Aedes* M-loci exhibit features of a proto-Y chromosome, including auxiliary sex-promoting genes, suppressed recombination, and sequence repeats (Chen et al., 2022; Palatini et al., 2020). In *Aedes aegypti*, the M-locus also includes *myo-sex*, a gene required for male flight, exemplifying how full male function depends on several M-linked components (Krzywinska et al., 2016; Aryan et al., 2020). Unlike the degenerated Y chromosome, however, both sexes of *Aedes* mosquitoes retain two complete autosomal sets, making dosage compensation unnecessary (Krzywinska et al., 2016). As a result, transgenic expression of *nix* in *Aedes* genetic females successfully induces masculinization, while its CRISPR-mediated disruption in genetic males leads to feminization, yielding viable and fertile pseudomales (genetic m/m females masculinized by *nix*) and pseudofemales (genetic M/m or M/M males feminized by *nix* loss), respectively (Aryan et al., 2020; Lutrat et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022; Hempel, 2025).

The repetitive and hemizygous structure of the M-locus poses substantial challenges for molecular characterization and genome assembly. Even with long-read sequencing, contigs spanning the locus often remain fragmented or chimeric, complicating the design of specific guide RNAs and the interpretation of gene-editing outcomes. Cas9-mediated mutagenesis in such regions is constrained by high sequence similarity among repeats, which reduces targeting specificity and hinders

reliable genotyping (Rossato et al., 2023). Furthermore, editing repetitive regions may produce unintended large deletions, non-specific insertions, or inversions, making functional validation of editing outcomes particularly difficult.

To address these limitations, this chapter presents a bioinformatic characterization of the *Ae. albopictus* M-locus, defining its content and identifying validated fragments suitable for CRISPR-mediated homology-directed repair (HDR) knock-in aimed at linking a selectable trait (e.g., yellow rescue) specifically to males. The second part explores a complementary approach that leverages the M-locus-independent masculinization capacity of *nix*. This section characterizes pseudomales through RNA-seq analysis to profile their transcriptome and evaluate the autonomous regulatory influence of *nix* in a genetic female background. Together, these analyses enhance understanding of M-locus architecture and function while revealing how *nix* reshapes gene expression, establishing the foundation for developing male-specific recovery systems in *Aedes*.

5.2 Results

5.2.1 Identification and verification of M-locus–derived sequences

Given the incomplete representation of the *Ae. albopictus* M-locus in the *AalbF2* genome assembly, the first objective was to identify and verify M-locus-derived sequences. Comparative analyses of male and female whole-genome sequencing (WGS) data were conducted to identify male-linked scaffolds, followed by molecular validation of their sex specificity. These verified sequences served as candidates for later targeting and functional testing

In the *AalbF2* genome assembly, the male-determining factor *nix* is located on scaffold NW_021838423 (916,555 bp; ranked 261 by size, hereafter “scaffold 261”). To identify regions potentially linked to the M-locus, whole-genome sequencing (WGS) reads from adult males and females were mapped to scaffold 261 and to a length-matched control region on scaffold NW_021837046 (34,012,471–34,929,027), which was selected randomly to serve as an autosomal reference. The proportion of nucleotide positions covered by at least one read was

higher in males ($94.0 \pm 0.52\%$) than in females ($75.6 \pm 0.47\%$), a difference that was significant according to a Wilcoxon test ($W = 0, p < 0.001$). The control region showed no significant sex difference (female $52.0 \pm 6.7\%$; male $65.7 \pm 9.9\%$; $W = 36, p = 0.721$) [Fig 5.1A]. Regions of at least 100 bp covered in all male libraries

Figure 5.1: Read coverage surrounding the *nix* scaffold reveals elevated male coverage and male-specific regions.

A) Proportion of scaffold coverage by male (blue) and female (pink) whole-genome sequencing (WGS) libraries for the *nix*-bearing scaffold 261 and a control region of equivalent length from scaffold 2. Coverage is defined as the percentage of scaffold positions with at least one mapped read. Error bars represent standard error of the mean, and an asterisk indicates a significant difference (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $p < 0.001$). B) Distribution of mapped reads along a 100 kb segment of scaffold 261. Due to graphical constraints, the maximum read depth per position is capped at 50. Black arrows denote male-unique clusters (MCs), and the yellow rectangle marks the annotated position of the male-determining factor *nix* gene.

were defined as canonical regions. Of 2,255 canonical regions on scaffold 261, 287 (12.7 %) were exclusive to males, corresponding to 9.2 % of the scaffold length. Most male-specific regions (84.7 %) occurred within the first 210 kb upstream of *nix*, with only two detected in the distal 3' 500 kb. Male-exclusive and canonical regions of ≥ 500 bp in size were classified as male clusters (MCs), and regions of similar size containing < 50 bp of mapped female reads were classified as semi-clusters (SCs) [Fig 5.1B]. Scaffold 261 contained 17 MCs and 7 SCs; two MC overlapped *nix* and its upstream regulatory region. RNA-seq mapping (Gamez et al., 2020) showed substantial transcription for seven clusters. PCR assays using genomic DNA from both sexes confirmed male-specific amplification for nine of the 15 tested clusters.

[Table 5.1; Fig 5.2]

Table 5.1: Evaluation and validation of putative HDR knock-in targets within the *nix* bearing scaffold on AalbF2 genome assembly.

Cluster (ID)	<i>Nix</i> proximity (Kb)	Size (bp)	Expression levels (RNAseq)				PCR validation
			Male	Female	Larvae	Embryo	
MC01	-200.1	813	44	41	24	815	All males
MC02	-192.6	498	4	3	2	14	All males
MC03	-176.4	647	6	0	3	17	All males
MC04	-174.6	655	65	90	20	273	All males
MC05	-168.2	531	5	5	6	12	Female band
SC01	-144.1	1359	0	25	0	5	Some males
SC02	-140.1	1275	3	1	4	1	Female band
SC03	-135.3	853	0	0	0	0	Female band
SC04	-130.9	779	0	90	1	0	Female band
SC05	-120.6	905	2	1	0	2	Female band
MC06	-113.3	919	19	50	6	69	All males
MC07	-83.7	621	16	17	11	17	Female band
MC08	-76.2	967	8	43	2	20	All males
SC06	-65.9	1192	6	22	9	44	Not tested
MC09	-63.9	557	41	66	12	105	Not tested
MC10	-39.0	541	3	43	1	6	All males
MC11	-24.3	529	31	29	1	97	Not tested
SC07	-27.8	967	8	1	28	101	All males
MC12	-20.7	1126	146	260	82	447	Not tested
MC13	-4.6	2313	20	4	17	85	All males
MC14	+34.3	1024	880	9	0	16	Not tested

MC17	94.7	813	20	157	29	110	No bands
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Regions ≥ 500 bp consistently present in all male whole-genome sequencing reads mapped to scaffold 261. These were classified as male clusters (MCs) if no female reads were mapped or semi-clusters (SCs) if female reads spanned < 50 bp. The table summarizes the cluster's position, RNA-seq expression levels on various samples and PCR-based validation for male specificity (presence only in males) and consistency (presence in all male samples) as exemplified in the figure 5.2 below

Fig. 5.2 PCR confirmation of M sequences in scaffold 261.

Representative PCR amplifications are shown for six out of fifteen sequences suspected to be M-derived, categorized as male clusters (MC) or semi-male clusters (SC). Each electrophoresis lane represents DNA amplified from either a single yellow male (δ^A , δ^B), a single wild-type female (δ^A), or a pool of ten wild-type females (δ^P). Amplification of *nix* and *yellow* served as controls.

Genome-wide coverage analysis is computationally demanding. Therefore, a complementary chromosome-quotient (CQ) analysis was performed using only annotated coding sequences (CDS), which represent approximately 2–3% of the *Ae. albopictus* genome. CQ values were calculated as the ratio of normalized female to male read coverage for each gene. Regions with low CQ values indicate male-biased read representation, whereas $CQ \approx 1$ corresponds to autosomal or shared sequences. Across 25,088 annotated single-copy genes that met the minimal read coverage, the CQ distribution identified 345 M-linked candidates ($CQ \leq 0.2$) and 1,307 m-linked candidates ($CQ \geq 2$), with the remaining $\sim 93.4\%$ considered autosomal [Fig. 5.3]. The lowest CQ value (0.0024) corresponded to *nix* on scaffold 261. Genes with low CQ values were distributed across 80 scaffolds. Nine of these contained clusters of more than ten such genes and often displayed local blocks of low-CQ values, consistent with possible scaffold chimerism.

Figure 5.3: *nix* is the gene with the lowest chromosomal quotient (CQ) value in the assembly.

Coding sequences (CDS) from the *Ae. albopictus* reference genome (AalbF2) were classified based on CQ values. Predicted M-linked (Y-chromosome-derived) sequences are shown in blue, autosomal genes in grey, and m-linked (X-chromosome-derived) sequences in red. **A)** Number of genes mapped to each category. **B)** Relative coverage (total mapped reads per gene) within each category. The M-linked male-determining factor *nix* and two autosomal genes, *yellow* and *myo-sex* are highlighted. Genes filtered out due to low coverage in male libraries appear as transparent.

Within the latter, low CQ genes were often clustered together [Fig 5.4]. This distribution of M-derived genes supports the assumption regarding contig misassembly and formation of chimeric scaffolds. These within-scaffold M-predicted gene congregations prompted further analysis to verify additional suitable knock-in targets. For that, a library of male unique k-mers (sequences exist exclusively in male WGS libraries) were mapped to 12 such scaffolds [Table 5.2].

Figure 5.4: Clustering pattern of gene with similar chromosomal quotient (CQ) across different scaffolds.

Scaffolds with low mean CQ scores exhibit two distinct patterns: **A**) Short scaffolds (<1M bp) containing several annotated genes. These typically include M-derived genes (blue, CQ score <0.2) and autosomal genes (grey, CQ score between 0.2 and 2). This group also includes the *Nix*-bearing scaffold, which is highlighted in light blue. **B**) Long scaffolds (>5M bp) with many annotated genes. These scaffolds typically display a chimeric CQ pattern, sometimes featuring distinct clusters of M-predicted genes (blue), autosomal genes (gray), and m-predicted genes (red, CQ score <0.2). The X-axis represents gene position, while the Y-axis and color denote CQ values. The right-side grey ribbon indicates the scaffold ID.

This analysis reveals varied distributions of male-exclusive reads, forming male clusters of different sizes across different scaffolds. The proportion of the scaffold consisting of male-exclusive reads varies significantly, from a low of 0.43% (NW_021838568) to a high of 37.67% (NW_021838467). Scaffolds exhibiting a higher percentage of male-exclusive reads consistently demonstrated both an increased total number of male-specific read clusters and a greater prevalence of large clusters (exceeding 1Kb in length).

Table 5.2: Male unique read distribution across different scaffolds

Scaffold ID	Length (Kb)	Total M (Kb)	%M	Male Clusters				PCR valid.
				> 0.5 Kb >	> 1Kb >	> 2Kb >	>4Kb	
NW_021838421	11,967	835	6.97%	257	123	34	3	2 / 10
NW_021838423*	917	85	9.22%	24	4	4	0	-
NW_021838438	844	179	21.15%	54	25	4	0	-
NW_021838467	769	290	37.67%	73	44	19	2	1 / 10
NW_021838492	714	61	8.50%	15	8	5	0	-
NW_021838521	8,124	677	8.33%	185	108	31	3	4 / 10
NW_021838568	574	2	0.43%	1	0	0	0	-
NW_021838571	557	139	24.99%	32	19	6	0	-
NW_021838676	5,617	1,253	22.30%	418	169	38	5	3 / 10
NW_021838701	401	136	33.90%	40	20	5	1	2 / 10
NW_021838875	268	72	27.02%	22	12	5	0	-
NW_021838949	232	20	8.62%	7	0	0	0	-
NW_021838987	2,943	636	21.61%	188	96	32	1	1 / 10

Proportions of male-specific unique reads across scaffolds were calculated as the total length of male-unique reads divided by the scaffold length. Additionally, sequential regions (>500 bp) composed exclusively of male-specific reads were defined as male clusters and categorized into four size groups. The Nix-bearing scaffold (scaffold 261) is marked with an asterisk and highlighted in blue for distinction. The last column indicates how many from the tested clusters were successfully *in vitro* validated as male-specific

For instance, scaffolds NW_021838467 (37.67% male-exclusive sequence) and NW_021838676 (22.30%) contained the most extensive male-specific regions, characterized by numerous large clusters. Conversely, scaffolds with a minimal percentage of male-exclusive reads, such as the aforementioned NW_021838568, demonstrated a scattered coverage pattern with very few clusters and lacked any clusters exceeding 1 kilobase in length. The robust positive correlation between the percentage of male-exclusive reads and the abundance of large clusters suggests that scaffolds enriched in male-specific sequences likely represent authentic M-locus contigs or significant portions thereof. Indeed, *in vitro* verification by PCR of clusters larger than 4Kb have successfully confirmed 13 potential M-locus knock-in targets [Table 5.2].

5.2.2 Targeting the M-locus for knock-in using HDR

Homology-directed repair (HDR) donor constructs were designed to target four validated M-locus fragments identified earlier in this study. Two such targets correspond to the nix bearing scaffold 261, and other two derived from scaffolds identified through CQ analysis [Table 5.3]. For each target region, approximately 1.0–1.5 kb left and right homology arms were amplified from genomic DNA of wild-type *Ae. albopictus* and inserted into donor backbones containing an *Opie2*-driven DsRed fluorescent marker. The resulting plasmids were verified by restriction digestion and Sanger sequencing to confirm correct arm orientation and junction integrity. Donor plasmids were co-injected with RNP of Cas9 and a single-guide RNA (sgRNA) designed to cut within the male-linked region.

Table 5.3: Knock-in targets, homology arms design and outcome

Scaffold	sgRNA PAM:position	Homologous region (Left ; Right)	Total injected eggs	GFP+ G0 males	GFP+ F1
NW_021838423	ACATTAGGGGAGGGGGAATA <u>GGG</u> : 187,406	186,169-188,515 (1.1Kb; 1,1.1Kb)	4,422	132	0
NW_021838423	GCGCTCATGAATGTTCTTGA <u>GGG</u> : 33,360	32,169-34,766 (1.2Kb; 1.4Kb)	1,980	79	0
NW_021838521	AGAATGCAGCGCAGCGTGAG <u>CGG</u> : 1,468,963	1,467,680-1,470,756 (1.2Kb; 1.8Kb)	1,980	84	0
NW_021838701	ACCTTGTTGACTACAACGT <u>TGG</u> : 357,802	356,018-360,451 (1.8Kb; 2.6Kb)	858	32	0
		Σ	9,240	327	0

For each knock-in site on the various scaffolds, the sgRNA target sequence (including the PAM site, underscored) and its genomic coordinates are listed. Corresponding left and right homology arms are shown with their coordinates and relative sizes. The total injection embryos, recovered transient G0 and transgenic F1 are indicated for each knock-in site. Bottom line summarises overall microinjection effort.

A total of 9,240 embryos were injected across twelve independent sessions, targeting four distinct M-locus sites. Surviving transient G0 males were mated in bulk to WT virgin females, followed by screening for transgenic F1 larvae. However, despite these efforts, no transgenic individuals were obtained.

5.2.3 Transgenic *nix*-based masculinization

The lack of successful HDR-mediated integration at the M-locus prompted a strategic pivot toward an alternative method for achieving male-specific recovery. Subsequent experiments employed a transgenic approach leveraging *nix*-induced masculinization. This method may circumvent the need to secure an M-locus integration by reintroducing *nix* along with another gene within a single transgenic construct.

Previous work in *Ae. aegypti* demonstrated that ectopic *nix* expression masculinizes genetic females, whereas the absence of *myo-sex* renders these pseudomales flightless. In *Ae. albopictus*, the *myo-sex* ortholog (LOC109430926) exhibited a CQ score of 1.11, indicating an autosomal location rather than M-linked [Fig 5.3B]. Accordingly a YRN construct was generated by fusing *nix* (isoforms 3 and 4, including 2 kb of upstream regulatory sequence) with the HspYR mini-*yellow* rescue cassette, thereby linking masculinization with pigment restoration as a visible marker [Fig. 5.5A]. Embryo injections produced seven independent transgenic families (YRN1–YRN7). In each family, males or pseudomales were repeatedly backcrossed to *yellow* females to establish a sexing strain producing dark, eGFP-positive males and yellow, eGFP-negative females [Fig. 5.5B]. Sex ratios in the F₁ generation were analyzed using binomial generalized linear models (GLMs). Four lines—YRN1, YRN3, YRN6, and YRN7—displayed significant male bias, with estimated male proportions of 0.744, 0.829, 0.909, and 0.844, respectively (all $p < 0.001$) [Fig. 5.5C]. Focus was placed on transgenic males from the YRN-6 family. Molecular genotyping confirmed the absence of endogenous *nix* in these individuals, indicating complete loss of the native M-locus [Fig. 5.6]. Consequently, males of this

Figure 5.5: Combining mini-yellow rescue and sex conversion.

A) Structure of the YNR construct created by adding *nix* isoforms 3 and 4 to the HspYR plasmid, which contains the *hsp83*-driven *mini-yellow* and the eGFP transformation marker.

B–D) Crossing scheme for isolating functional integrations.

B) Transgenic male isofounders are crossed with *yellow* females. **C)** F1 progeny were analyzed for sex and transgenic status.

D) F2 transgenic males from isofamilies with significant sex bias (Z-test, $p < 0.05$ indicated by *) were individually crossed to *yellow* females to exclude subfamilies producing transgenic females or *yellow* individuals and to purify M-locus free male lineages by molecular genotyping for the endogenous *nix* and *yellow*.

E) Sex conversion and *yellow* rescue in crosses between YRN and *yellow* females, using HspYR as a control. Frequency of pigmentation phenotypes (dark and *yellow*) separated by sex in progeny are shown with error bars representing standard error and numbers indicating the total individuals recorded per group.

lineage were defined as pseudomales. To validate the functionality of the YRN construct as a sexing system, *yellow* females were crossed either to YRN-6 pseudomales or to HspYR-1 males, which carry only the *hsp83*-driven mini-*yellow* rescue cassette. In crosses involving HspYR-1, dark and yellow phenotypes segregated equally among male and female pupae ($\chi^2 = 2.21$, $p = 0.137$). In contrast, all females from YRN-6 crosses were yellow, whereas all phenotypically male pupae were dark ($\chi^2 = 1747$, $p < 0.001$) [Figure 5.5E].

Figure 5.6: Molecular confirmation of absence of functional yellow allele or endogenous *nix* among YRN6.

A) Schematic of three yellow alleles and the YRN construct with corresponding and discriminative PCR primers. A WT male chromosome (y^+ ; M) containing the native yellow gene and *nix* (~81 Mb upstream). A mutant female chromosome (y ; m) lacking the M locus and containing a mutant yellow allele. The masculinizing mini-yellow YRN construct contains an intron-less mini-yellow driven by the *hsp83* promoter and contains the *nix* 3&4 isoform from Lutrat et al., 2022. Alleles or constructs can be differential detected - only WT yellow (grey), M-linked *nix* (teal), all yellow alleles (yellow), mini-yellow (orange), and YRN-*nix* (red). **B)** Gel electrophoresis of PCR products from single and pooled genomic DNA samples. Lanes are separated by a 1 kb ladder (GeneDirex, Taiwan).

A small proportion of transgenic individuals (4.2%) exhibited intersex phenotypes characterized by intermediate genitalia, antennae, and mouthparts. These intersexes were unable to blood-feed or mate [Figure 5.7]. Despite this minor proportion of abnormal individuals, the strong and consistent linkage between melanization and masculinization in YRN-6 established a functional pseudomale-based *yellow* GSS.

Figure 5.7: Morphological sexual dimorphism and intersex phenotype.

Each panel shows a schematic silhouette (top) and a representative photograph (bottom) of an adult mosquito. Sexually dimorphic features are highlighted: abdominal terminalia (blue), which in males bear paired mating claspers; the antennae (yellow), which are densely plumose in males and sparsely so in females; and maxillary palps (red), which are elongated in males but vestigial in females. A) Wild-type male displaying all three male-characteristic features. B) Wild-type female displaying the corresponding female-characteristic features. C) Intersex individual exhibiting intermediate morphology across all three features. The $\times 2$ inset shows a magnified view of the abdominal terminalia, revealing a malformed single clasper structure.

5.2.4 Transcriptomic analysis of pseudomale-based GSS

Although *Aedes* mosquitoes have homomorphic sex chromosomes, they show clear morphological and physiological sexual dimorphism that results from sex-specific gene expression. Pseudomales express the male-determining factor *nix* but are genetically *m/m* females that lack the M-locus present in true *M/m* males. To evaluate the extent of masculinization and residual femininity in this strain, mRNA sequencing was performed on whole-body RNA extracted from wild-type males, wild-type females, GSS pseudomales, and GSS females.

Genome-wide expression profiles provided an overview of similarities within and between groups. Replicates within each group were highly consistent. GSS females

showed the highest mean Spearman correlation ($r_s = 0.984 \pm 0.0023$), followed by GSS pseudomales (0.978 ± 0.0002), wild-type males (0.973 ± 0.0017), and wild-type females (0.973 ± 0.0011). Between-group comparisons showed that the closest similarity occurred between females of the two strains ($r_s = 0.957 \pm 0.0005$), indicating that the *yellow* mutation had little influence on global transcription. The next most similar groups were GSS pseudomales and wild-type males ($r_s = 0.955 \pm 0.001$), showing that *nix* masculinization largely reproduces the male transcriptome. Within-strain comparisons between sexes showed that wild-type males and females were slightly more correlated ($r_s = 0.881 \pm 0.0019$) than GSS pseudomales and GSS females ($r_s = 0.880 \pm 0.002$). The resemblance of GSS pseudomales to wild-type females ($r_s = 0.868 \pm 0.0015$) was lower than that of wild-type males to wild-type females, further distinguishing pseudomales from females [Fig. 5.8A]. To describe the underlying differences in gene activity, differential-expression analysis was conducted. Comparison between wild-type males and females produced a catalog of *Ae. albopictus* sex-associated markers. These were genes showing sex-specific or significantly sex-biased expression and represented 12.1 % of the 17,189 expressed genes. The catalog contained 859 male-biased and 1,228 female-biased genes. To determine how the pseudomale transcriptome compared with these markers, expression levels of genes in GSS pseudomales were compared with those of wild-type females [Fig. 5.8B]. The results showed that most markers retained their original sex bias: 623 (72.5%) male markers and 917 (74.7%) female markers remained classified as such, while the remainder were reclassified as neutral (222 male and 309 female markers). Among the genes that preserved their original expression profiles were male-associated genes involved in spermatogenesis, such as *tubulin beta chain* (LOC109414298), *testis-specific serine* (LOC109425165), *sperm flagellar protein* (LOC109417052), and *tektin-1* (LOC109418945). Female-specific genes included *vitellogenin-A1* (LOC109413684), *chorion peroxidase* (LOC109399009), *odorant receptor Or2* (LOC109416825), and *apyrase-like* (LOC109425975) preserved their female-biased expression despite the pseudomales genetic female background. These findings confirm that *nix* expression drives extensive masculinization of the transcriptome while repressing major female genes. Loss of sex bias in some female markers might have been expected from gene dosage in the m/m background. However, their annotation showed an even

distribution among chromosomes 1, 2 and 3 (100, 100 and 102 genes respectively) and seven on unplaced scaffolds, indicating that double dosage does not explain this pattern [Fig. 5.8C].

Figure 5.8: GSS pseudomale demonstrates high degree of transcriptomic masculinization.

RNA-seq was performed on whole-body RNA from three biological replicates per group: wild-type males (Blue), wild-type females (Pink), GSS pseudomales (Teal), and GSS females (Yellow). A) Spearman correlation matrix of genome-wide expression across all samples and replicates. Color intensity reflects the degree of transcriptomic similarity, with gray shades indicating lower correlation values (r_s closer to 0.8). B) Differential expression analysis comparing WT females versus WT males (top) or GSS pseudomales (bottom). The native male- (blue) and female- (pink) associated markers and their transition or retention between the two analyses are indicated. C) Chromosomal distribution of transitioning differentially expressed genes and the mean CQ score \pm Std.err of the transitioning group D) Log₂ fold-change between the WT sexes for male-markers (blue) or females-markers (pink) that either maintained their sex-bias when comparing GSS pseudomales to WT females or became neutral (unbiased). Significant differences are indicated by letter annotations (ANOVA: $F_{(3,2067)} p < 0.0001$ Tukey's HSD test $\alpha = 0.005$).

Analysis of fold-change trends showed that genes retaining sex specificity had significantly larger expression differences than those that became neutral (ANOVA $F(3, 2067)$ $p < 0.0001$; Tukey-Kramer HSD $\alpha = 0.05$). This means that strong bias is more likely to be preserved [Fig. 5.8D]. Only two female markers were expressed at higher levels in pseudomales than in females, one of them *yellow*. Eleven male-biased genes were not detected in pseudomales, which suggests linkage to or regulation by the M-locus (Table 5.3). Three male-biased genes shifted to female-biased expression: *Cytochrome P450 9E2* (LOC109426418) and two uncharacterized proteins, LOC109416324 and LOC109418009. The two unknown proteins carry domains of uncertain function (DUF4495 and DUF1759). *Cytochrome P450 9E2* contains a PHD-finger DNA-binding motif and also lacked expression in *yellow* GSS females, suggesting that its regulation may be affected by the *yellow* mutation. None of these genes were located within the 1.3 Mb region postulated to contain the M-locus [Fig. 5.9A]. To verify possible M-linkage, chromosome-quotient analysis and mapping of male-specific k-mers were applied to this group of genes [Table 5.4]. The results were confirmed by PCR, which verified that five of the eleven genes were male-linked [Fig. 5.9B]. Four of these five genes were protein-coding: LOC109432934 (annotated as *let-4* like), LOC134285312, LOC134289344, and LOC134285028. Pfam motif searches indicated that these encode proteins with leucine-rich repeat, sperm-tail, and YqaJ-like recombinase domains, while LOC134285028 lacked recognizable motifs.

Possible incomplete masculinization could also affect splicing of sex-determination genes. To test this, expression and splicing of *nix*, *doublesex (dsx)*, *fruitless (fru)*, *myo-fem*, *myo-sex*, and *yellow* were examined. As expected, *nix* was not expressed in wild-type or GSS females, while both wild-type males and pseudomales showed clear coverage across *nix* exons. In pseudomales, reads were limited to the two exons included in the transgene (isoforms 3 and 4). Splicing of *dsx* and *fru* followed the male pattern, omitting female-specific exons. The female muscle gene *myo-fem* was not expressed, whereas its male paralog *myo-sex* was active. Mapping these reads to *yellow* showed higher expression of the transgenic rescue allele than of the endogenous gene, consistent with transcription from the constitutive *hsp83* promoter. A local drop in coverage was seen in GSS females at the sgRNA target site,

Table 5.4: Bioinformatic properties of lost male markers

LOC ID (size bp)	Name (Biotype)	pfam motifs	logTPM male	logTPM female	logTPM ps.male	CDS CQ score	mRNA CQ score	M k-mers coverage	PCR validation
109402953 (4,085)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	PF12032; PF00089	27.8 ± 10.1	0	0	0.34572	0.312511	262	Not specific
109432934 (4,025)	<i>let-4-like</i> (protein coding)	PF13855; PF12799	21.2 ± 8.4	0	0	0.02277	0.01169	2418	M. specific pattern
115263956 (372)	uncharacterized (ncRNA)	non_coding	182 ± 95.5	0	0	NA	NA	0	Not specific
134284628 (980)	uncharacterized (ncRNA)	non_coding	3.5 ± 0.8	0	0	NA	0.86593	0	Not specific
134285028 (176,349)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	none identified	29.9 ± 1.1	0	0	0.41816	0.46404	0	M. specific pattern
134285312 (1,112)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	PF14775; PF04849; PF19042	29.7 ± 8	0	0	0.27699	0.71116	87	M. specific pattern
134285501 (1,654)	uncharacterized (ncRNA)	non_coding	1.8 ± 0.4	0	0	NA	1.03768	49	Not specific
134287234 (3,013)	uncharacterized (ncRNA)	non_coding	20.5 ± 5.9	0	0	NA	0.77869	0	M. specific pattern
134288451 (4,797)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	PF00628; PF03564; PF13650	3 ± 1.9	0	0	0.67926	0.86432	0	Not specific
134289344 (3,169)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	PF09588	5.2 ± 1.4	0	0	1.19457	1.23525	0	M. specific pattern
134291881 (3,013)	uncharacterized (protein coding)	PF05699	5.5 ± 2.2	0	0	0.91760	0.90297	0	Not specific
109402083 (27,166)	<i>yellow</i> (protein coding)	PF03022	66.5 ± 30.1	741.63 ± 69.1	67725.3 ± 1263.3	1.40162	1.50547	0	Not specific
109397226 (160,456)	<i>nix</i> (protein coding)	PF00076; PF16367	1.78 ± 0.727	0	8.35 ± 0.962	0.001176	0.0011757	29368	M. specific pattern

List of genes expressed exclusively in wild-type (WT) male libraries. For each gene, the *AalbF5* assembly annotation is provided, including gene size, biotype, predicted name and function. Identified Pfam motifs (for coding genes only) are included. Shown are total RNA-seq reads from male, female, and pseudomale libraries, the calculated Chromosomal Quotient (CQ) based on previously published WGS data, and the total base pairs corresponding to k-mers detected exclusively in male WGS libraries.

consistent with indels in the *yellow* mutant alleles [Fig. 5.10]. These results demonstrate *nix* capabilities of reprogramming the female *Ae. albopictus* transcriptome toward a predominantly male pattern, maintaining the expression of male-biased genes while repressing key female genes, consistent with its central role in male sexual differentiation.

B

Figure 5.9: In-silico localization and molecular validation of male-specific markers in AalbF5 chromosome assembly.

A) Chromosomal mapping of male-markers across Chromosomes 1, 2, 3, and unplaced scaffolds, with Nix in aqua and the putative 1.3Mb M-locus highlighted in light blue. Markers are color-coded by differential expression (DE) status in pseudo-males: retained DE (blue), neutralized DE (grey), acquired female-markers (pink), and lost expression (black), with the latter annotated using 5-digit LOC numbers. Gene orientation is indicated by triangle direction. **B)** Gel electrophoresis of PCR amplicons from wild-type male (M) and female (F) genomic DNA, testing the eleven lost male markers. Yellow and nix serve as autosomal and M-specific controls, respectively; underscored IDs denote confirmed male-specific amplification patterns.

Figure 5.10: Single-Nucleotide Resolution RNA-Seq Coverage of Sex-Specific Genes. RNA-seq reads coverage for key sex determination genes (*nix*, *doublesex*, *fruitless*) and known sex-associated markers (*myo-fem*, *myo-sex*, and *yellow*). Exons are represented by grey boxes, with female-specific exons highlighted in pink (Note: introns are not drawn to scale). Read coverage is color-coded by sample type: male (blue) and pseudo-male (teal) libraries are displayed on the positive Y-axis, while wild-type female (pink) and GSS female (yellow) libraries are shown on the negative Y-axis for visual clarity. Dashed Rectangle boxes display an enlarged section of interest within the genes. Coverage tracks represent reads per position, derived from HISAT2-aligning normalized to library size.

5.3 Discussion

The development of GSS for *Ae. albopictus* represents an important advancement toward introducing sex-specific traits in non-model organisms. This work combined long-read genome assembly, coverage-based analyses, and transcriptomic profiling to identify male-specific genomic regions and to test whether the male-determining factor *nix* alone can generate a functional sexing system. Together, these approaches exposed both the structural complexity of the M-locus and its biological implications for future strain design.

Using the AalbF2 assembly (Palatini et al., 2020) and high-resolution coverage comparisons between male and female whole-genome sequencing data, distinct male-exclusive regions were identified on scaffold 261, which also contains *nix*. Most of these regions, approximately 85 percent, were located upstream of *nix*, suggesting that the gene lies near the boundary of the M-locus or, more likely, that scaffold 261 represents a chimera combining M-linked and autosomal segments. Similar assembly artifacts have been described for sex-determining regions in other genome assemblies (Hoskins et al., 2015; Nurk et al., 2022). The chromosome quotient (CQ) method offers a complementary approach for identifying sex-chromosome associated sequences using normalized library read counts (Hall et al., 2013, 2015, 2016). In this study, CQ analysis identified approximately 360 candidate M-linked genes and over 1,400 m-linked genes distributed across 80 scaffolds. However, assuming even gene distribution across the genome, a 1.3 Mb region such as the M-locus is expected to contain fewer than 30 coding genes. Although this approach provided a broad overview of potential sex-linked loci, it clearly inflated the number of M-linked candidates. This inflation reflects both technical and biological factors. Technically, the CQ metric is sensitive to repetitive DNA, uneven GC content that leads to library sequencing bias, and scaffold chimerism, all of which characterize the *Aedes* genome. Multi-mapping reads can be unevenly assigned to single scaffolds, and local coverage biases can shift female-to-male ratios away from unity even for autosomal loci. Biologically, the presence of paralogous gene families and partial duplications can mimic male or female linkage when one copy differs in copy number or expression between sexes.

For these reasons, CQ alone cannot reliably define M-specific or m-derived genes without independent support from complementary analyses such as male-specific k-mer searches, mappability filtering, and validation through transcriptomic and comparative PCR assays.

Combining all these approaches yields a more conservative list of a small number of genes within the M-locus. This outcome is consistent with findings in other dipterans, where male-determining regions and Y chromosomes often contain few genes but are enriched in repetitive DNA. For example, the *Anopheles* Y chromosome carries only a few functional genes despite spanning tens of megabases (Hall et al., 2016). Functional activity in such regions is often maintained through non-coding mechanisms. In *Drosophila*, Y-linked repetitive sequences generate piRNAs that silence X-linked genes essential for spermatogenesis (Adashev et al., 2021; Venkei et al., 2023), and analogous mechanisms may operate in *Aedes* (Biedler et al., 2024). This possibility suggests that even though few protein-coding genes are present, the M-locus may still play essential regulatory roles through factors acting in trans to influence genes elsewhere in the genome. The present transcriptomic analysis was limited to polyadenylated mRNA, and therefore does not capture the potential contribution of small non-coding RNAs to sex-specific gene regulation. Small RNA sequencing, particularly of piRNAs and miRNAs, could provide additional insight into the regulatory landscape of the M-locus and its downstream targets. Profiling small RNA populations across wild-type males, wild-type females, and GSS pseudomales could reveal whether M-locus-derived non-coding RNAs contribute to the expression differences observed here, and whether their absence in pseudomales accounts for any of the eleven male-biased genes that were undetected in this strain.

The repeated failure of homology-directed repair (HDR) integrations into the M-locus further reflects its heterochromatic and non-recombining nature. This resistance to targeted knock-in is consistent with the scarcity of successful Y-chromosome integrations reported in insects. To date, stable Y-linked knock-ins have been achieved only in *Drosophila melanogaster* (Gamez et al., 2021), despite extensive efforts by multiple research groups to reproduce this success in other species. A plausible explanation for this failure is that HDR, which depends on homologous

recombination, is suppressed in this genomic region, while the error-prone non-homologous end-joining (NHEJ) pathway predominates during double-strand break repair (Jasin and Rothstein, 2013). Future strategies may involve transient inhibition of NHEJ components such as Ku70 or Lig4 (Basu et al., 2015), or the adoption of NHEJ-based integration systems that have proven effective in other insects (Bosch et al., 2020; Matsuoka et al., 2025). Another possibility is that integration events did occur but were transcriptionally silenced by the dense heterochromatin surrounding the M-locus, a form of position-effect variegation already observed in several dipterans (Gray & Coates, 2004; Lynd & Lycett, 2012; Elgin & Reuter, 2013; Berloco et al., 2014; Gamez et al., 2021). In principle, M-linked integration could also be achieved through transposon-mediated random piggyBac insertion. A transgene that integrates by chance within the M-locus might achieve linkage with maleness. However, the low recombination rate characteristic of *Aedes* would make it difficult to predict or ensure the long-term stability of such linkage under mass-rearing conditions. It should be acknowledged that no positive control experiment establishing HDR-mediated integration at a permissive genomic locus was included in parallel with the M-locus knock-in attempts, and no *in vivo* cutting assays were performed to independently validate sgRNA efficiency prior or after embryo injections in this work. The absence of these controls means that a contribution of technical failure to the observed outcome cannot be entirely excluded. However, the recovery of 327 transiently expressing G0 males across twelve injection sessions provides indirect evidence that the injection procedure was functional and that the constructs were delivered successfully into embryos. Furthermore, to date no successful HDR-mediated genomic integration has been reported in *Ae. albopictus*, suggesting that this species may be broadly refractory to homology-directed repair regardless of the target locus. The consistent failure to recover stable transformants across four independent M-locus target sites may therefore reflect a species-wide limitation rather than a locus-specific one, though further experiments including sgRNA validation and integration attempts at a validated permissive autosomal loci would be required to distinguish between these possibilities.

Because of these obstacles, the study pursued a transgenic approach independent of the native M-locus. By combining *nix* with a mini-*yellow* rescue cassette and introgressing this construct into a *yellow* mutant background, a stable strain was generated that produces dark, eGFP-positive males and yellow, eGFP-negative females. This design couples masculinization with a visible marker, providing an operational GSS without requiring M-locus integration. The transgenic *nix* construct was sufficient to masculinize genetic females and produced viable and reproductive functional pseudomales. This result contrasts with the flightless pseudomales observed in *Ae. aegypti*, where *myo-sex* is M-linked. As demonstrated in previous studies, in *Ae. albopictus*, *myo-sex* appears to be autosomal, explaining the retention of flight capability. Transcriptome analysis confirmed that pseudomales displayed extensive masculinization, with about 74 percent of sex-biased genes maintaining their original male or female expression patterns. Most genes that lost sex bias remained expressed but became gender-neutral rather than reversed, indicating stochastic variation rather than incomplete masculinization.

A small group of eleven male-biased genes was not detected in pseudomales. Five of these were confirmed as M-linked based on PCR and read-mapping evidence, suggesting that they depend on M-specific regulatory sequences or additional factors absent from the *nix* transgene. One of these genes, *LOC134285312*, encodes a sperm-tail domain protein and may contribute to fertility. The remaining undetected genes may be regulated by M-linked elements or masked by autosomal paralogs with high sequence similarity. This finding emphasizes the need to complement *nix*-based systems with additional male-function genes or regulatory components when designing future GSS strains. Incorporating such elements into future masculinizing rescue cassette designs may be necessary to recover more of the male-biased markers that have lost their sex-specific expression in pseudomales.

A minor proportion of YRN-6 pseudomales, about four percent, exhibited intersex features such as intermediate genitalia and antenna morphology. These phenotypes may result from multiple insertion events of the transgene that created mosaic expression, or from alleles within the laboratory strain that partially counteract transgenic *nix* activity (Krzywinska et al., 2016). Further genetic and phenotypic

characterization is needed to determine whether these individuals arise from variable transgene dosage, incomplete splicing regulation, or background genetic modifiers.

The combined findings demonstrate that a *nix*-based system can effectively substitute for the native M-locus in producing viable, flight-capable pseudomales. The strong correlation between the pseudomale and wild-type male transcriptomes confirms that *nix* is the primary driver of male differentiation in *Ae. albopictus*, but the absence or mis-expression of some genes implies that other M-locus factors contribute to complete male functionality. Identifying these components will be essential for improving transgenic sexing systems and ensuring their stability and fitness under field conditions. Beyond its applied implications, this research provides insight into how male determination can persist through minimal genomic content, revealing how sex determination systems evolve and remain functional despite extreme structural reduction.

Chapter III - Benchmarking of the Genetic Sexing Strain

6.1 - Introduction

In this study, a genetic sexing strain (GSS) was developed for *Aedes albopictus* using transgenic expression of the male-determining factor *nix*. In this species, *nix* can fully transform genetic females into fertile phenotypic males (Lutrat et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022). To establish the GSS, a homozygous line for the *yellow* loss-of-function mutation was generated. A transgenic construct containing *nix* together with a *yellow* rescue cassette was then introgressed into the background of homozygous *yellow* females. This produced a strain in which pigmentation is exclusively associated with pseudomales (masculinized females), whereas females retain the bright yellow phenotype.

In theory, such *yellow*-based GSS offers advantages for operational sexing, as it produces a reliable, non-lethal, and vividly distinguishable phenotype that can be recognized throughout development, from larvae to adults. The trait could also serve as a quality-control marker in size-based separation, which remains the most widely used sexing method to date. Nevertheless, its suitability for integration into operational sexing systems still requires critical evaluation.

The establishment of any GSS requires careful evaluation of its overall performance, as genetic modifications can influence fecundity, longevity, and mating competitiveness (Williams et al., 2023). Previous studies have shown that *nix*-transformed pseudomales are comparable to wild-type males in body size, fertility, and flight ability (Lutrat et al., 2022) but display reduced mating success (Lutrat et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022). These parameters should therefore be re-evaluated for the *yellow*-based GSS to assess its suitability for operational deployment.

Proper development under mass-rearing conditions, efficient sex separation, and competitive mating performance are the primary requirements for any prospective GSS. Accordingly, this chapter provides a detailed characterization of the *yellow*-based GSS based on these quality criteria. First, developmental and

morphological traits are compared between the GSS and wild-type mosquitoes. Second, the reliability and operational value of the female-specific *yellow* phenotype as a selectable marker for sexing are evaluated. Finally, the mating competitiveness of pseudomales is assessed to determine their potential for field deployment. Beyond its immediate application to the *yellow*-based GSS, this chapter establishes a framework for evaluating future markers in *nix*-based sexing systems.

6.2 - Results

6.2.1 Morphometrics and Developmental Dynamics

Sexual dimorphism in *Aedes* mosquitoes, particularly the smaller size of male pupae and their faster development, forms the basis of traditional mechanical sex-separation methods. To assess the compatibility of the yellow GSS with such approaches, wild-type (WT) and GSS larvae were co-reared in the same tank under mass-rearing density conditions. A total of 4,557 pupae were collected, and a representative subsample of 33.3% (1,517 pupae) was analyzed morphometrically. The analyzed group included 537 WT males, 382 GSS males, 340 WT females, and 195 GSS females that were successfully imaged and measured.

The principal morphometric trait used in size-based sex separation, such as with the Fay–Morlan glass separator, is the pupal cephalothorax width. Morphometric analysis showed no significant difference between WT and GSS males, with mean cephalothorax widths of 0.940 mm and 0.937 mm, respectively. In contrast, WT female pupae were slightly but significantly smaller than GSS females, with mean widths of 1.086 mm and 1.110 mm, respectively (Tukey–Kramer HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$; Cohen's $d = 0.39$) [Fig. 6.1A]. This difference resulted in a 16% increase in sexual size dimorphism in the GSS strain compared with the WT.

Color quantification further revealed significant variation in mean gray value among the four sex–strain groups (Tukey–Kramer HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$) [Fig. 6.1B]. GSS females were the brightest, with a mean gray value of 212 ± 15.2 , followed by GSS males (173 ± 8.8), WT males (164 ± 7.1), and WT females (149 ± 8.1), which were the darkest. Overall, the GSS displayed a 60% greater color dimorphism compared with the WT. The combined effect of enhanced size and color dimorphism reduced the

overlap of morphological features between the sexes in the GSS strain, improving the potential for both manual and automated sex discrimination [Fig. 6.1C].

Figure 6.1: Enhanced sexual dimorphism of yellow-GSS.

Measurements of **A)** Pupal pigmentation intensity (mean grey value) and **B)** pupal width (mm). Statistical significance for both metrics was determined using ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD test, with significant differences indicated by letter groups ($p < 0.05$). Error bars indicate standard error. **C)** Combined analysis of width and pigmentation levels. Each point represents an individual pupa, with histograms showing the distribution of phenotypes.

Across all replicates, only 20.3% of the 4,557 pupae collected were GSS yellow females [Fig. 6.2A]. Analysis of developmental timing showed that this underrepresentation resulted from slower development in GSS females. Daily pupal collections over one week from the onset of pupation revealed significant differences among the four strain–sex groups (ANOVA, $F(3, 4550) = 578.01$, $p < 0.001$) [Fig. 6.2B]. The delay led to consistent underrepresentation of GSS females across all replicates ($\chi^2 = 2.98$, $p = 0.0067$). GSS pseudomales pupated slightly earlier than WT males, while GSS females pupated significantly later than WT females (Welch's t-tests: males, $t(2369) = 3.07$, $p = 0.0021$; females, $t(2048) = -11.28$, $p < 0.0001$).

Specifically, GSS females reached pupation at 8.31 ± 0.04 days post-hatching, compared with 7.69 ± 0.04 days for WT females. No developmental delay was observed in GSS males relative to WT males.

Figure 6.2: Developmental differences between WT and GSS strain.

A) Developmental duration of co-reared WT and GSS strains, measured as the mean number of days from egg hatch to pupation. Statistical significance was determined by Welch's t-test (* $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$). Error bars represent standard error of the mean. **B)** Pupation dynamics over time. Kernel density plots illustrate daily pupation probability for each sex:strain group. Semi-transparent areas represent the four experimental replicates, and solid lines indicate cumulative probability.

Together, the morphometric and developmental differences indicate that the yellow GSS strain amplifies the naturally occurring sexual dimorphism observed in the wild-type. The combination of a greater size difference between males and females, enhanced color contrast, and the delayed pupation of GSS females effectively widens the temporal and morphological gap between the sexes. This observation prompted further investigation into whether the developmental delay reflects a consistent form of sexual bimaturism and whether it could enhance male-biased collection efficiency under mass-rearing conditions.

6.2.2 Sexual Bimaturism

Sexual bimaturism, defined as the natural difference in developmental timing between males and females, manifests in *Aedes* mosquitoes as protandry, where males pupate earlier than females. This characteristic is routinely exploited in mass-rearing programs to increase the proportion of males collected for release. To determine whether the developmental delay observed in GSS females also occurs

under pure-strain rearing conditions and whether it could reduce female contamination in large-scale rearing, pupation timing was monitored in triplicate high-density trays for both WT and GSS strains. Pupae were collected multiple times daily to improve temporal resolution, yielding a total of 7,439 individuals across ten collection events [Fig. 6.3A]. The combined effect of faster GSS male and slower

Figure 6.3. Enhanced protandry of *yellow*-GSS reduces female contamination.

A) Pupation dynamics tracking male recovery and female contamination for WT and GSS strains across three replicates per strain. **B)** Delay in female pupation relative to males, expressed as a percentage increase in developmental time (protandry index). Error bars represent standard error of the mean. **C)** Male recovery rates at three levels of female contamination, comparing WT and GSS males.

GSS female development increased the protandry index to 27.8 ± 0.82 in the GSS compared with 17.4 ± 0.29 in the WT. Consistent results were obtained in replicated high-density rearing assays, which again revealed significant strain–sex differences

in pupation timing (Welch's t -test, $t(3,3896) = 11.282$, $p < 0.001$). Female pupation in the GSS required approximately 40% longer than in the WT **[Fig. 6.3B]**, resulting in an improved protandry index of 26.2 ± 0.08 versus 19.4 ± 0.59 in the WT. From a practical standpoint, this enhanced protandry increased male recovery efficiency, since at any given threshold of acceptable female contamination, the GSS consistently yielded a higher proportion of males than the WT **[Fig. 6.3C]**.

6.2.3 Sexing Performance

To determine whether the enhanced sexual dimorphism in the yellow GSS improves the accuracy and speed of sex separation, a controlled sexing trial was conducted. Seven researchers with prior experience in mosquito colony maintenance were asked to manually sort pupae from either the WT or GSS strains under two conditions: naked-eye observation and under a dissecting microscope. The duration of the sorting procedure and the accuracy of sex identification were used to assess sexing efficiency. The time required to sex GSS pupae was significantly shorter. The average per-individual sorting speed (measured as seconds per pupa) was roughly twice as fast for GSS compared with WT pupae, regardless of the observation method (t -test, $t_{13} = -7.32$, $p < 0.001$) **[Fig. 6.4A]**. In terms of accuracy, misclassifications occurred only in WT samples, where females were occasionally identified as males. This type of error was recorded in one of the sorting sessions using optical magnification and in all sessions performed under naked-eye conditions. No misclassifications were observed in any of the GSS sorting sessions. Overall, sorter precision was significantly higher for the GSS compared with the WT (paired t -test, $t_{13} = 3.37$, $p = 0.005$) **[Fig. 6.4B]**, confirming its fitness for purpose.

Figure 6.4: The GSS improves both speed and precision of the sexing procedure.

A) Sexing speed for WT (grey) and GSS (green) pupae under naked-eye and dissecting microscope settings. Error bars denote standard error. **B)** Sexing session aftermath, showing the proportion of pupae correctly classified as males (blue) or females (red) by seven insectary staff (A–G) for WT and GSS strains under both settings. Diagonal hatching indicates misclassifications resulting in either male loss or female release. The total pupae in each sample are indicated in each bar.

6.2.4 Mating Competitiveness

Mating competitiveness is a critical parameter for evaluating the feasibility of genetic control interventions. It reflects the ability of released males to successfully mate with and inseminate females when competing against wild-type (WT) males, thereby determining the number of released individuals required to achieve population suppression. To assess the competitiveness of *yellow* GSS pseudomales, four-day-old males from co-reared GSS and WT larval trays were introduced into competition cages, followed by the addition of virgin females. Competitiveness was calculated based on the proportion of transgenic larvae produced and the relative proportion of GSS pseudomales among the parental males in each cage. Three mating competitiveness experiments were conducted, varying in cage density, number of biological replicates, and release ratios summarized below [Table 6.1].

Table 6.1: Parameters, outcomes, and competitiveness calculations for mating assays.

Trail	Release rate (GSS:WT)	Density (n / Liter)	Biological Replicates	Females per cage	Total L1	% WT	Comp.
1	0.5	5.06	1	25	569	96.8%	0.135
	1	6.75	1	25	983	87.8%	0.323
	2	5.06	1	25	1026	77.3%	0.416
2	0.5	3.24	4	12	1604	95.8 ± 2.6%	0.203 ± 0.13
	1	3.24	3*	16	1634	87.3 ± 4.12%	0.376 ± 0.16
	2	3.24	4	12	1309	77.2 ± 2.9%	0.450 ± 0.10
3	1	6.08	8	30	10677	91.9 ± 1.6%	0.205 ± 0.04
	5	6.11	8	30	9619	66.1 ± 1.5%	0.468 ± 0.07

Parameters and results from three mating trials evaluating yellow GSS male competitiveness against WT males. Release ratio (GSS:WT) shows the proportion of GSS to WT males released. Density (mosquitoes/liter) indicates the cage predicted encounter rate, and biological replicates show cage numbers (asterisk denotes outlier omission). Total L1 is the number of screened first-instar larvae, % WT is the wild-type larva proportion, and Comp. is the adaptation for Fried's competitiveness index value (standard error value was indicated where applicable).

The combined mean competitiveness across these experiments was 0.353 ± 0.043 . However, in all experiments, the calculated competitiveness of GSS pseudomales was positively and significantly correlated with their relative proportion in the cage

(Pearson's $r = 0.364$, $t(28) = 2.07$, $p = 0.0477$). This result was unexpected, as competitiveness is considered an intrinsic property of a strain and should not depend on the release ratio, a parameter already accounted for in the calculation. To investigate this discrepancy, a mating simulator was developed in R. The simulation reproduced 1,000 iterations in which 25 *in silico* females were introduced into virtual cages containing digital males at four GSS:WT release ratios (0.5, 1, 2, and 5) and a gradient of 100 possible GSS male competitiveness values ranging from 0.01 to 1.00. The F1 transgenic proportion produced by the model fit to the experimental data were evaluated using the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), and the corrected Akaike information criterion (AICc). The experimentally derived competitiveness calculation was supported by the model, with the best fit obtained at a competitiveness value of 0.32, corresponding to the lowest RMSE (0.0575) and a strong R^2 (0.771). Competitiveness values of 0.33 and 0.35 also produced similarly good fits, with RMSE values of 0.0576 and 0.0578 and R^2 values of 0.770 and 0.768, respectively. However, fixed competitiveness value cannot explain the observed dynamic between competitiveness and release ratio. The density-dependent pattern, in which GSS males became less competitive at low release ratios and more competitive at high ones, suggested that the release ratio influenced the transgenic composition of the F₁ through secondary mating attempts by females. Such female behavior is more likely to be affected by the relative abundance of GSS males in the cage. Accordingly, the *in silico* model was adjusted to simulate sequential mating under two alternative scenarios: (i) a polygamous female, where females can mate multiple times, allowing post-mating competition between sperm from GSS and WT males with differing fertilization success; and (ii) a reluctant female model, where monogamous females decline an initial mating attempt if the courting male is a pseudomale. The model iterated 1,000 times for each release ratio, testing four pre-defined competitiveness levels for pseudomales (0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1.0). Two parameterizations produced the best fits to the experimental data. The first scenario, involving polygamous females with a pseudomale mating and post-mating competitiveness of 0.5, achieved the lowest RMSE (0.048) and highest R^2 (0.842). The second scenario, with fully competitive pseudomales (competitiveness = 1.0) but a subset of reluctant females, produced a comparable fit (RMSE = 0.05, $R^2 = 0.824$) [Fig. 6.4].

Figure 6.4: *In silico* model simulation fitted to the observed outcomes of mating competitiveness trials.

The proportion of GSS pseudo-males' offspring in the F1 generation (Y-axis) as a function of their relative proportion in the competition cage (X-axis), simulated across four competitiveness levels (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00). Data points represent experimental observations from three mating competitiveness experiments (Table 6.1), with fitted lines illustrating model predictions for two different female mating behaviors. Dashed lines represent polygamous female behavior, with colors indicating varying post-mating competitiveness of pseudo-males. Solid lines depict monogamous female behavior, with a pink line indicating permissive (non-selective) mate choice and a black line representing reluctant females that reject their first mating opportunity with pseudo-males. R² values reflect the goodness of fit for each competitiveness level, with the best fit for each female mating model highlighted.

To determine which of the two competing explanations best accounts for the observed mating dynamics, namely (i) polyandrous females with GSS pseudomales exhibiting reduced pre- or post-mating competitiveness, or (ii) monogamous, reluctant females with fully competitive GSS males, empirical assays were conducted to quantify female remating frequency and pattern.

In these assays, virgin females were first mated with either transgenic “WT” males expressing dsRED or GSS pseudomales expressing eGFP and were subsequently exposed to males of the opposite type in reciprocal crosses. The transgenic fluorescence profiles of the resulting F_1 progeny were analyzed to determine paternity and identify potential sequential inseminations. Two complementary experiments were performed. In the bulk-mating assay, females were collectively exposed to males, and F_1 larvae were screened from pooled ovitank collections. In the individual-female assay, single females were mated and their clutches analyzed separately. No evidence of remating was detected in the bulk assay, as all offspring carried the marker of the first male [Fig. 6.5A]. In the individual-female assay, sequential insemination was rare, observed in only three of forty females, and remating frequency did not differ significantly between females that initially mated with pseudomales or wild-type males (logistic regression: $\beta = -0.747$, $SE = 1.268$, $z = -0.589$, $p = 0.556$). These isolated cases did not indicate any reduction in the post-mating competitiveness of GSS pseudomales. Collectively, the results suggest that remating is unlikely to explain the density-dependent variation observed in measured mating competitiveness [Fig. 6.5B]. The most plausible explanation for the observed results is therefore monogamous reluctant-female behavior.

Figure 6.5 Paternity outcomes in successive mating assays.

A) Group-mating (bulk) assay showing the transgenic composition of F₁ larvae produced by females first mated to GSS pseudomales carrying the eGFP marker (left) or to wild-type males carrying the dsRED marker (right). Each bar represents progeny from one technical repeat (ovitank). **B)** Individual-female assay showing the progeny composition of 40 females whose first mating partner (P₁) was either a GSS pseudomale (left) or a true male (right). Each bar represents one biological replicate (female), with stacked fluorescence classes indicating the proportion of larvae sired by the first or second male. Stars mark the three females whose progeny carried mixed fluorescence markers, indicating re-insemination.

6.3 - Discussion

The comprehensive evaluation of the yellow-based GSS for *Ae. albopictus* demonstrates its strong potential as a next-generation platform for genetic control programs (de Araújo et al., 2018). The strain combines a clear visual sex marker with enhanced morphological and developmental dimorphism, addressing one of the key bottlenecks in mosquito population suppression strategies: accurate and efficient sex separation (Papathanos et al., 2018).

The GSS exhibited markedly enhanced sexual dimorphism compared with the wild-type (WT) strain, showing a 16% increase in size dimorphism and a 60% increase in color contrast between the sexes. The bright yellow loss-of-function phenotype of females, easily distinguishable from the darker WT background, substantially improved sorting performance. Sorting speed doubled relative to WT pupae, and no misclassifications were recorded even under naked-eye inspection. Given the naturally occurring size overlap between the sexes (Zacarés et al., 2018), which results in residual female contamination during size-based sex sorting (Gunathilaka et al., 2019), the added color trait provides an independent and reliable second dimension for separation. This improvement directly benefits manual sexing procedures, reducing labor, error rate, and processing time in mass-rearing facilities where pupal sorting is a major operational constraint (Lutrat et al., 2019). Although reliance on manual sexing is decreasing in modern SIT programs, automated sex-sorting systems are also expected to benefit from this additional dimension either for reducing sorting error, or improving human-based quality control of the output (Crawford et al., 2020).

When co-reared with the WT strain, yellow GSS females exhibited delayed development, leading to their underrepresentation among emerging pupae. However, this delay disappeared when the strain was reared in isolation, indicating that the slower development was not intrinsic but rather caused by interstrain competition, likely due to limited access to food when reared alongside WT females. Within the GSS itself, pseudomales and yellow females developed without any evidence of delay, supporting the conclusion that the strain carries no inherent fitness penalty. The observed dynamics are consistent with earlier findings (This

study, chapter 1), which showed that yellow females experience delayed development only in mixed rearing. Despite the absence of intrinsic developmental delay, the GSS displayed stronger sexual bimaturism than the WT. The faster development of pseudomales and the relatively slower development of females resulted in a 40% increase in the protandry index. This expanded temporal gap between the sexes enhances the operational utility of the strain, allowing earlier male collection with reduced female contamination (Bellini et al., 2018). Under fixed thresholds of acceptable contamination, male recovery efficiency was consistently higher in the GSS, providing a clear advantage for mass-rearing programs that depend on early pupal collection to produce male-only cohorts.

The mating competitiveness of GSS pseudomales averaged 0.353 ± 0.043 , a level lower than that of WT males but higher than previous estimates for *Ae. albopictus* pseudomales (Lutrat et al., 2022). In that earlier study, only a 1:1 release ratio was tested, producing a competitiveness value of 0.224, similar to the 0.258 ± 0.036 average measured in the 1:1 cages of this work. It should be noted that the three competitiveness trials were conducted several months apart, which likely contributed to the substantial inter-experiment variance observed at equivalent release ratios. A retrospective power analysis indicated that the study achieved a power of 0.52 for the reported correlation between competitiveness and release ratio ($r = 0.364$, $n = 30$, $\alpha = 0.05$), falling below the conventional threshold of 0.80. The positive correlation between competitiveness and release ratio should therefore be interpreted as a preliminary finding, and future experiments conducted under standardized conditions within a single trial and with larger sample sizes would be required to confirm this relationship with adequate statistical power. Nevertheless, the consistency of the directional trend across all three independent experiments provides some confidence that the observed pattern reflects a genuine biological phenomenon rather than a statistical artifact. A similar density-dependent relationship between release ratio and measured competitiveness has been previously reported in *Wolbachia*-infected and irradiated *Aedes males* but remained unexplained (Zhang et al., 2016, Kittayapong et al., 2019; Bond et al., 2021; Kittayapong et al., 2025). Since competitiveness should not theoretically depend on the proportion of released GSS males (Gentile et al., 2015), possible explanations for this trend were explored further using *in silico* modeling.

Simulation analyses identified two potential behavioral explanations for the density-dependent pattern: (i) post-mating sperm competition under conditions of female re-insemination, or (ii) female reluctance to mate with pseudomales during initial encounters. Although *Aedes* females are generally considered monogamous, evidence of re-insemination has been recorded in crowded laboratory conditions and in the field (Boyer et al., 2012; Oliva et al., 2013; Yamada et al., 2024). The refractoriness assay provides direct empirical evidence bearing on this question: co-insemination events were scarce, undetected among 5,268 insemination events in bulk mating experiment, and observed in only three out of forty females that were individually assessed, in which no apparent reduction in pseudomale sperm competitiveness was detected. This makes a post-mating competitiveness handicap an unlikely explanation for the density-dependent pattern, and instead supports the reluctant-female model, which assumes active female mate choice (Edward & Chapman, 2011; Castellano et al., 2012; Hourii-Zeevi et al., 2025). According to this model, pseudomales are comparable to WT males in initiating courtship, but their copulation attempts are typically accepted only after a female has previously interacted with a pseudomale. The likelihood of such repeated encounters increases with the release rate of GSS males and may account for the calculated rise in their competitiveness. Such female behavioral plasticity has broader implications for genetic control programs, as female mating strategies can substantially affect the outcome of male-release interventions and should be considered when designing and evaluating their efficacy (Sutter et al., 2021). While this interpretation remains preliminary pending further experimental validation, it aligns with conditions typical of genetic control programs, where high GSS male release densities are expected to generate frequent pseudomale–female interactions (Wang et al., 2021).

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that GSS pseudomales are fully capable of mating and inducing female refractoriness, suggesting functional equivalence to WT males once mating occurs. The density-dependent improvement in competitiveness further indicates that the strain would perform effectively under operational release scenarios that involve high male-to-female ratios. Future experiments should validate these outcomes in semi-field and large-cage environments, where environmental variables such as temperature, humidity, illumination, and spatial structure can

influence mating success (Facchinelli et al., 2013; Madakacherry et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2016; Mamai et al., 2016). The strain's compatibility with geographically distinct or wild-derived female populations should also be tested to confirm its utility in diverse release sites.

In conclusion, the yellow-based GSS represents a substantial advance for genetic control of *Ae. albopictus*. It offers enhanced visual sexing efficiency throughout the mosquito ontogeny, maintains adequate mating competitiveness, and exhibits no intrinsic developmental cost. The strain's inability to produce eggs tolerant to mild desiccation further supports its suitability for incompatible insect technique (IIT) applications, where preventing establishment of released mosquitoes in the field is essential (Zeng et al., 2022). While the strain is technically ready for integration into mass-rearing pipelines, its final deployment will depend on performance evaluations under industrial production scale, semi-field trials and regulatory considerations due to its transgenic nature. Importantly, the use of endogenous components such as *Nix* and *yellow* provides a foundation for cisgenic design (Boomika et al., 2025) that avoid foreign sequences and may facilitate regulatory approval and public acceptance.

Chapter 7 - General discussion

For more than four decades, the VIENNA-8 Genetic Sexing Strain (GSS) of the Mediterranean fruit fly (*Ceratitis capitata*) has served as the benchmark for insect sex separation. Its simple, sex-linked selectable trait provided an enduring foundation for large-scale Sterile Insect Technique (SIT) programs (Franz, 2005). Despite many efforts to reproduce comparable systems in other insect species, progress remained limited, restricted by the unpredictability of classical forward genetics.

Mosquito control programs have therefore relied on natural dimorphisms for female elimination, most commonly exploiting the slightly larger size of female pupae. Yet this method is inherently constrained: male and female size distributions overlap (Zacarés et al., 2018), both sexes must be reared to the pupal stage before separation (Franz et al., 2021), and manual sorting is labor-intensive. Although automated systems have been developed, they remain expensive and technically demanding (Crawford et al., 2020). A genetically engineered sexing system would overcome these limitations by enabling precise, scalable, and reproducible separation (Papathanos et al., 2018).

This study explored a novel platform for developing GSSs in the arboviral vector *Aedes albopictus*. The approach combines CRISPR-mediated disruption of a native gene encoding a selectable trait with its genetic rescue linked to a sex-converting transgene, thereby generating a strain in which the rescue is confined to one sex. The highly conserved *yellow* (*y*) gene, first identified in Thomas Hunt Morgan's fly room, was selected as a proof of concept for this system. More than a century after this sex-linked phenotype was first described in *Drosophila*, this work used modern molecular tools to recreate the recessive mutation in mosquitoes and invert its sex specificity, as originally described by Morgan:

“A male appeared in the black-winged stock with golden yellow wings. In fact, the entire fly is conspicuously yellow, and makes a striking contrast with his dark companions. He was bred to his black sisters, and gave only black flies in the first generation. These were inbred and have produced 233 black

females, 127 black males and 76 golden-winged males. Evidently the color is sex-limited in relation to the melanic type from which it arose.”

(Morgan, 1911)

The *yellow* gene was selected for its vivid phenotype, simple structure, and prior studies in *Aedes* mosquitoes showing that null mutants exhibit a visible phenotype throughout development with no reported fitness cost (Liu et al., 2019). Ortholog analysis, sgRNA design, and on-target CRISPR mutagenesis successfully reproduced the *yellow* phenotype in the FPA laboratory strain. However, this study uncovered a previously unreported fitness cost associated with this mutation: severe desiccation intolerance in eggs. Desiccation-resistant, dormant eggs are a key factor in the global dispersal and establishment of *Aedes* mosquitoes and are routinely exploited in mass-rearing facilities to synchronize production cycles (Bellini et al., 2018). Although egg vulnerability presents a logistical challenge, it can be mitigated through modified storage protocols (Zheng et al., 2015). Importantly, this sensitivity may also serve as an intrinsic biosafety feature in Incompatible Insect Technique (IIT) programs by preventing the persistence of accidentally released females (Zeng et al., 2022).

To restore the wild-type phenotype, two rescue constructs encoding an intron-deprived *mini-yellow* sequence were generated. The endogenous rescue (EnYR), which used native regulatory regions, failed to restore pigmentation, suggesting that key regulatory elements were absent. In contrast, the heat-shock rescue (HspYR), driven by regulatory regions from the *hsp83* gene, successfully restored pigmentation in the *yellow* mutant background. RNA-seq confirmed strong *mini-yellow* expression in adults, indicating that the *hsp83* promoter is an effective driver for selectable traits requiring broad expression.

To achieve sex-specific rescue through homology-directed repair (HDR) at the M-locus, potential insertion sites were identified by integrating multiple bioinformatic resources. In vitro validation of these predictions yielded twenty-one candidate regions suitable for HDR. However, knock-in attempts at four of these sites were unsuccessful, suggesting that the M-locus may be resilient to recombination-dependent integration (Rai et al., 2016). Nonetheless, the validated

candidate sequences constitute a valuable resource for future knock-in efforts employing alternative integration strategies (Matsuoka et al., 2025).

To overcome the resistance of the M-locus to knock-in, *nix* was integrated into the *mini-yellow* construct, thereby linking masculinization with pigmentation rescue (YRN construct). Introgression of this construct into the recessive *yellow* background led to the establishment of a genetic lineage in which both *yellow* and *nix* functions were entirely transgene derived. Only one of the seven isofamilies produced fertile pseudomales, indicating that transgenic *nix* expression is highly susceptible to position effect variegation (Berloco et al., 2014). The successful generation of a *nix*-dependent, M-locus-free strain represents a genuine pseudo-male-based GSS. This approach avoids the fertility loss associated with reciprocal translocations, and circumvents the technical limitations of sex-chromosome knock-ins, constrained by the heterochromatic and repeat-rich nature of such loci (Vicoso, 2019). It also addresses a persistent limitation of Y-linked integrations, which may display unstable or variegated transgene expression (Gamez et al., 2021). In contrast, *nix*-based sex conversion establishes a stable, autosomal route to male development, providing a practical and reliable alternative for sex-chromosome integration (Lutrat et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022).

To date, no other insect species has exhibited a comparable degree of permissiveness to M-factor mediated sex conversion as *Aedes albopictus*. Even the closely related *Ae. aegypti* produces pseudomales that are flightless (Aryan et al., 2020). In most insects, expression of master male-determining genes in genetic females does not result in fertile or viable males, either because additional Y-linked factors are required for complete male development or because overactivation of X-linked genes leads to lethality or severe developmental defects (Kalita & Valsecchi, 2025). The ability of *nix* to induce complete masculinization of genetic females in *Aedes albopictus* is therefore exceptional. Furthermore, transcriptomic analyses conducted in this study revealed that pseudomales closely resemble wild-type males in their gene expression profiles, including correct splicing of key sex-determining genes such as *dsx* and *fru*. While most sex-biased genes maintained their expected expression patterns, eleven were undetected in pseudomales, five of which were confirmed to originate from the M-locus. The

functions of these genes, and their potential roles in male fertility, merit further investigation.

From an operational standpoint, males of the GSS strain were indistinguishable from wild-type males in larval development time and pupal size, indicating that no developmental or size-related fitness costs are associated with GSS pseudomales. This also confirms the strain's compatibility with size-based sex separation methods. The pronounced color contrast between males and females provides an additional, highly reliable dimension for sex discrimination, markedly improving both the speed and accuracy of sex sorting. Another advantageous feature of this GSS is its enhanced protandry relative to the wild-type strain, with yellow female larvae requiring approximately 40% more time to pupate. This developmental delay substantially reduces the proportion of residual females among collected pupae and increases overall male recovery from rearing trays.

Improved rearing efficiency and reliable sex separation are intrinsic indicators of GSS performance; however, mating competitiveness remains the decisive factor for its effectiveness in field deployment and ultimately defines the required production scale. Previous studies have concluded that pseudomales are less competitive than true males when competing for females (Lutrat et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022). The present work represents the first attempt to quantify this disadvantage and propose a plausible underlying mechanism. Consistent with earlier observations, true males outperformed GSS pseudomales in mating trials. However, this handicap was significantly and inversely correlated with the proportion of pseudomales in the cage. Similar phenomena have been reported in sterilized and *Wolbachia*-infected *Aedes* males (Zhang et al., 2016; Kittayapong et al., 2019; Bond et al., 2021; Kittayapong et al., 2025), although no mechanistic explanation was proposed. In this study, three independent mating experiments, together with an *in silico* mating model developed specifically for this work, showed that pseudomales were comparable to wild-type males in their ability to intercept and initiate courtship with females (at least under small-cage laboratory conditions) and in their capacity to induce post-mating female refractoriness. These two traits are among the most critical determinants of success in suppressive genetic control interventions. According to the model, the reduced competitiveness of GSS pseudomales stems from reluctant female behavior, where

receptivity is modulated by prior exposure. After rejecting a pseudomale during the first encounter, a female is more likely to accept courtship from another pseudomale in a subsequent interaction. Such behavioral plasticity in female mate choice (Castellano et al., 2012; Watts et al., 2022) may help explain the success of genetic control interventions even when released males exhibit extremely low mating competitiveness (Harris et al., 2012; Bouyer & Vreysen, 2020). Further evaluation of pseudomale mating performance in different settings and against field-derived males and females instead of laboratory colony will be essential to validate the predictive power of the model and to assess the robustness of this GSS for population suppression applications.

The growing global threat posed by mosquitoes and mosquito-borne diseases continues to drive the development of innovative tools for population suppression, including several repressible strategies reported in the past year (Zhang et al., 2024; Bouyer et al., 2025; Verkuil et al., 2025; Strampelli et al., 2025). Yet, despite their technological diversity and distinct modes of action, the large-scale implementation of all these approaches still depends on a reliable and sustainable method for sex separation. This study establishes a versatile framework for developing pseudomale-based genetic sexing strains (GSSs). The successful recreation of the *yellow* gene mutation in *Aedes albopictus* marks an important milestone toward high-throughput sexing systems and provides a practical platform for identifying potent, inducible selectable traits. For example, traits such as the temperature-sensitive lethal (*tsl*) mutation recently characterized in the Mediterranean fruit fly (Aumann et al., 2025), or the extensive repertoire of comparable lethal mutations described in *Drosophila* (Grigliatti et al., 1973), could be adapted for mosquito control. Although the functionality of these orthologs may vary among species, their successful implementation in *Ae. albopictus* strengthens the potential for effective translation to other mosquito vectors. Collectively, this work provides a robust foundation for future GSS innovations, extending beyond *Ae. albopictus* and advancing the broader field of genetic control in mosquitoes.

8. References

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Supplementary Statistical Appendix

S1. Chapter I — Engineering a Selectable Trait

S1.1 Development Time

S1.1.1 Single-strain rearing

Two-way ANOVA on development time (days from hatch to pupation) with phenotype (yellow vs WT) and sex as fixed factors, single-strain rearing condition:

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	1.0	0.98	0.849	0.357
sex	1	241.0	241.01	209.194	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	0.6	0.58	0.505	0.477
Residuals	960	1106.0	1.15		

S1.1.2 Mixed rearing (co-reared)

Two-way ANOVA on development time with phenotype and sex as fixed factors, mixed rearing condition:

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	8.0	7.96	6.710	0.00976 **
sex	1	220.2	220.16	185.532	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	10.4	10.38	8.746	0.00319 **
Residuals	822	975.4	1.19		

Wilcoxon rank-sum test for co-reared WT vs yellow females: $W = 16633$, $p < 0.001$ (mean pupation time 7.62 ± 0.09 vs 8.00 ± 0.12 days).

S1.2 Body Size Morphometrics (yellow vs WT, co-reared)

Two-way ANOVA for each morphometric parameter with phenotype and sex as fixed factors. $n = 482$ co-reared pupae. HSD group letters indicate significant differences (Tukey HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$).

S1.2.1 Mean gray value (pigmentation intensity)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	356504	356504	5811.16	< 2e-16 ***
sex	1	9883	9883	161.09	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	1684	1684	27.45	2.67e-07 ***
Residuals	382	23435	61		

Group	Mean gray value	HSD group
yellow female	206.66	a
yellow male	200.52	b
WT male	150.24	c
WT female	135.73	d

S1.2.2 Pupal area (mm²)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	387	387	6.410	0.0117 *
sex	1	45737	45737	757.860	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	107	107	1.769	0.1843
Residuals	380	22933	60		

Group	Mean area	HSD group
yellow female	97.86	a
WT female	94.80	b
yellow male	75.00	c
WT male	74.05	c

S1.2.3 Pupal width (mm)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	0.30	0.2993	1.304	0.254
sex	1	3.11	3.1093	13.548	0.000266 ***
phenotype:sex	1	0.05	0.0548	0.239	0.625
Residuals	382	87.67	0.2295		

Group	Mean width (mm)	HSD group
yellow female	2.130	a
WT female	2.051	ab
yellow male	1.928	b
WT male	1.897	b

S1.2.4 Major axis length (mm)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	0.372	0.372	23.43	1.89e-06 ***
sex	1	12.123	12.123	762.47	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	0.209	0.209	13.12	0.000331 ***

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
Residuals	382	6.074	0.016		

Group	Mean major (mm)	HSD group
yellow female	2.898	a
WT female	2.791	b
yellow male	2.499	c
WT male	2.485	c

S1.2.5 Feret diameter (mm)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	0.332	0.332	24.538	1.1e-06 ***
sex	1	11.922	11.922	880.551	< 2e-16 ***
phenotype:sex	1	0.113	0.113	8.349	0.00408 **
Residuals	382	5.172	0.014		

Group	Mean Feret (mm)	HSD group
yellow female	2.794	a
WT female	2.702	b
yellow male	2.409	c
WT male	2.386	c

S1.3 Egg Storage and Desiccation Tolerance

ANCOVA with phenotype as fixed factor and storage duration (days) as continuous covariate, nested within plate (plate_id as error stratum):

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
phenotype	1	0.11777	0.11777	10.967	0.00388 **
storage_days	1	0.10423	0.10423	9.707	0.00597 **
phenotype:storage_days	1	0.01377	0.01377	1.282	0.272
Residuals	18	0.19329	0.01074		

Paired t-test comparing overall WT vs yellow hatching rates across all timepoints: mean difference = 0.526 (95% CI: 0.411–0.641), $t(11) = 10.06$, $p < 0.001$.

Tukey–Kramer HSD post hoc group assignments ($\alpha = 0.05$):

Group	Total eggs	Mean hatch rate	SE	HSD group
WT — 8 days	410	0.925	0.017	a
WT — 15 days	481	0.964	0.007	a
WT — 22 days	511	0.837	0.055	a
WT — 29 days	490	0.610	0.037	b
yellow — 8 days	413	0.595	0.018	b
yellow — 15 days	534	0.540	0.060	b
yellow — 22 days	328	0.092	0.053	c
yellow — 29 days	459	0.003	0.002	c

S1.4 Yellow Rescue Statistics

Chi-square test (Pearson, with Yates' continuity correction) comparing phenotype frequency distributions between transgenic and non-transgenic individuals:

Construct	X-squared	df	p-value	Interpretation
EnYR (endogenous promoter)	2.206	1	0.137	No rescue — dark and yellow frequencies not different from control
HspYR (hsp83 promoter)	1747	1	< 2.2e-16 ***	Full rescue — all transgenic individuals dark

S2. Chapter II — Male-Specific Recovery

S2.1 Transcriptomic Analysis — Spearman Correlation Matrix

Within-group and between-group Spearman correlation coefficients (r_s) computed from genome-wide expression profiles of three biological replicates per group. WM = wild-type male, GM = GSS pseudomale, WF = wild-type female, GF = GSS female.

S2.1.1 Within-group correlations

Group	Mean r_s	SD	SE
GSS females (GF)	0.9841	0.0040	0.0023
GSS pseudomales (GM)	0.9777	0.0004	0.0002
WT males (WM)	0.9734	0.0030	0.0018
WT females (WF)	0.9727	0.0020	0.0011

S2.1.2 Between-group correlations

Comparison	Mean r_s	SD	SE
WT female vs GSS female	0.9569	0.0016	0.0005
GSS pseudomale vs WT male	0.9554	0.0030	0.0010

Comparison	Mean rs	SD	SE
WT male vs WT female	0.8814	0.0058	0.0019
GSS pseudomale vs GSS female	0.8797	0.0060	0.0020
WT male vs GSS female	0.8675	0.0066	0.0022
GSS pseudomale vs WT female	0.8680	0.0045	0.0015

S2.2 Sex Conversion Statistics

Binomial generalized linear models (GLM) testing for significant male bias in F1 sex ratios across YRN transgenic lines. Lines with significant male bias ($p < 0.001$) were selected for further development: YRN1 (estimated male proportion 0.744), YRN3 (0.829), YRN6 (0.909), and YRN7 (0.844).

Chi-square test comparing pigmentation phenotype frequencies by sex in YRN-6 crosses vs HspYR-1 controls:

Cross	X-squared	df	p-value	Interpretation
HspYR-1 × yellow females	2.21	1	0.137	No sex-specific rescue — equal dark/yellow in both sexes
YRN-6 × yellow females	1747	1	< 2.2e-16 ***	Complete sex-specific rescue — all females yellow, all males dark

S3. Chapter III — Benchmarking of the Genetic Sexing Strain

S3.1 Morphometrics (GSS vs WT, co-reared)

Two-way ANOVA for each morphometric parameter with strain (GSS vs WT) and sex as fixed factors. $n = 1,517$ pupae analyzed. Three phenotype groups: yellow females (GSS females), transgenic males (GSS pseudomales), and WT males and females.

S3.1.1 Mean gray value (pigmentation)

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
strain	2	111462	55731	444.0	< 2e-16 ***
sex	1	39892	39892	317.8	< 2e-16 ***
Residuals	1064	133562	126		

Group	Mean gray value	HSD group
GSS female (yellow)	204.20	a
GSS pseudomale (transgenic)	172.61	b
WT male	164.40	c
WT female	148.74	d

S3.1.2 Pupal width (mm) — primary sexing metric

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
strain	2	15.50	7.751	34.24	3.43e-15 ***
sex	1	17.74	17.743	78.38	< 2e-16 ***
Residuals	1207	273.24	0.226		

Group	Mean width (mm)	HSD group
GSS female (yellow)	2.159	a
WT female	2.106	a
WT male	1.783	b
GSS pseudomale	1.775	b

Two-sample t-test comparing GSS pseudomale vs WT male cephalothorax width: $t = -0.236$, $df = 782$, $p = 0.813$ (not significant — GSS pseudomales indistinguishable from WT males by size).

S3.2 Developmental Dynamics (GSS vs WT, co-reared)

Two-way ANOVA on development time with strain \times sex interaction, including replicate as blocking factor:

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
strain	1	19	18.6	10.554	0.00117 **
sex	1	2858	2858.0	1623.025	< 2e-16 ***
replicate	3	16	5.4	3.087	0.02611 *
strain:sex	1	178	178.1	101.128	< 2e-16 ***
Residuals	4550	8012	1.8		

Tukey HSD post hoc group means (days from hatch):

Group	Mean (days)	SE	HSD group
GSS female	8.31	0.044	a
WT female	7.69	0.037	b
WT male	6.46	0.037	c
GSS pseudomale	6.29	0.040	d

Welch two-sample t-tests for individual sex comparisons:

Comparison	t statistic	df	p-value
GSS male vs WT male	3.074	2369.3	0.002136 **
GSS female vs WT female	-11.282	2048.3	< 2.2e-16 ***

S3.3 Sexual Bimaturism — Pure-Strain Rearing

SBM index calculated per replicate tank using the formula $SBM = 2(F - M) / (F + M) \times 100$, where F and M are mean female and male pupation times respectively.

Tank	Strain	Male pupation (days)	Female pupation (days)	SBM index
A	WT	6.42	7.72	18.39
B	WT	6.69	8.12	19.31
C	WT	6.78	8.33	20.52
D	GSS	5.95	7.74	26.15
E	GSS	5.82	7.57	26.14
F	GSS	6.17	8.04	26.32

Strain	Mean SBM	SE
WT	19.41	0.62
GSS	26.20	0.06

Two-way ANOVA on development time in pure-strain rearing with strain × sex interaction:

Source	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	Pr(>F)
strain	1	793	793	525.65	< 2e-16 ***
sex	1	4669	4669	3096.91	< 2e-16 ***
strain:sex	1	65	65	42.93	6.05e-11 ***
Residuals	7435	11210	2		

S3.4 Sexing Performance

Paired t-tests comparing GSS vs WT sorting performance across seven sorters under two conditions (optical magnification and naked eye). n = 14 paired observations per test.

Metric	GSS mean ± SE	WT mean ± SE	t statistic	df	p-value
Speed (sec/pupa)	1.816 ± 0.120	4.451 ± 0.358	7.321	13	< 0.001 ***
Precision (proportion correct)	1.000 ± 0.000	0.942 ± 0.017	-3.369	13	0.005 **

GSS precision was 1.000 in all 14 sorting sessions (no misclassifications). Misclassifications were recorded in 11 out of 14 WT sorting sessions. Mean fold-improvement in sorting speed: 2.57×.

Raw sorting data per sorter:

Sorter	Method	GSS sec/pupa	GSS precision	WT sec/pupa	WT precision
Denys	Optics	1.66	1.000	5.00	1.000
Dor	Optics	1.92	1.000	6.41	0.968
Doron	Optics	1.26	1.000	3.34	1.000
Gleb	Optics	1.73	1.000	2.95	0.988
Guy	Optics	1.79	1.000	4.40	1.000
Orr	Optics	2.13	1.000	4.93	0.986
Shira	Optics	2.19	1.000	5.63	0.989
Denys	Naked eye	1.28	1.000	7.07	0.798
Dor	Naked eye	1.50	1.000	3.82	0.944
Doron	Naked eye	1.87	1.000	2.63	0.942
Gleb	Naked eye	1.14	1.000	2.96	0.872
Guy	Naked eye	2.02	1.000	5.07	0.934
Orr	Naked eye	2.09	1.000	3.53	0.929
Shira	Naked eye	2.84	1.000	4.57	0.835

S3.5 Mating Competitiveness

Linear regression of observed transgenic offspring proportion as a function of GSS pseudomale release rate, across three independent competition experiments (n = 30 cages, excluding outliers and controls):

Parameter	Estimate	SE	t value	Pr(> t)
Intercept	-0.206	0.032	-6.436	5.70e-07 ***
release_rate	0.644	0.052	12.365	7.33e-13 ***

Model fit: Residual SE = 0.050, $R^2 = 0.845$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.840$, $F(1,28) = 152.9$, $p = 7.33e-13$.

Release rate	n cages	Mean transgenic proportion	SD	SE
0.333 (WT biased)	5	0.040	0.045	0.020
0.500 (Fair play)	12	0.096	0.052	0.015
0.667 (GSS biased)	5	0.227	0.051	0.023
0.833 (GSS release)	8	0.339	0.042	0.015

Pearson correlation between calculated competitiveness index and release ratio: $r = 0.364$, $t(28) = 2.07$, $p = 0.048$.

Retrospective power analysis for Pearson correlation ($r = 0.364$, $n = 30$, $\alpha = 0.05$, two-sided): achieved power = 0.52. This falls below the conventional threshold of 0.80, indicating that the correlation result should be interpreted as preliminary.

Logistic regression for female remating frequency as a function of first mate identity (pseudomale vs WT male): $\beta = -0.747$, $SE = 1.268$, $z = -0.589$, $p = 0.556$ (not significant). Re-insemination was observed in 3 of 40 females and did not differ significantly between groups.

Data Availability Statement

Raw Sequencing Data Raw RNA-seq reads generated in this study have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under BioProject accession PRJNA1100762. Libraries include three biological replicates per group for wild-type males, wild-type females, GSS pseudomales, and GSS females.

Construct Sequences and Maps The full annotated sequences of the EnYR, HspYR, and YRN constructs are publicly available as Supplementary Material in Zaada et al. (2025), *Nature Communications* (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-66940-0>). The M-locus HDR knock-in donor constructs are not deposited at this time, as they represent active experimental tools currently in use for ongoing work. They are available upon direct request to the corresponding author.

Mating Simulator R Code The R code for the *in silico* mating simulator described in Section 3.6 is currently withheld pending publication of an associated manuscript, upon which it will be made publicly available with a citable DOI. The model structure, parameterization, and behavioural scenarios are described in sufficient detail in Sections 3.6 and 6.2.4 to allow independent implementation. The full experimental dataset used to fit and evaluate the model is provided in the Supplementary Statistical Appendix. Researchers interested in collaboration or early access are welcome to contact the corresponding author directly.

Bioinformatic Pipeline Scripts The customized bioinformatic pipeline scripts used for CQ metric calculation, scaffold coverage analysis, and male-specific k-mer analysis were based on an established pipeline developed by F. Krsticevic. These scripts are available upon reasonable request to the aforementioned author.

Supplementary Data Tables All datasets supporting the analyses in this dissertation are deposited in Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19610162>), organized into three ZIP archives corresponding to the three data chapters. Each archive contains the relevant raw experimental datasets, construct sequence files in GenBank format, and bioinformatic output tables. A detailed description of each file is provided in the repository README. Full statistical model output tables are provided in the Supplementary Statistical Appendix (Sections S1–S3) of the dissertation.

Third-Party Data

Whole-genome sequencing libraries used for M-locus coverage analysis were obtained from Palatini et al. (2017) (NCBI BioProject PRJNA484104). RNA-seq libraries used for differential expression analysis were obtained from Gamez et al. (2020) (NCBI BioProject PRJNA563095).

תקציר

יתושות מהוות מטרד וסכנה מתמשכת לבריאותם ולרווחתם של מיליארדים. הקשיים הכרוכים בבקרת אוכלוסייתן באמצעים קונבנציונליים הובילו לפיתוחם של מגוון אמצעי בקרה העושים שימוש ביתושים זכרים מטופלים המדכאים את פוטנציאל הרבייה של אוכלוסיית הבר. יישום בטוח של אמצעי בקרה אלה, דורש הפרדה זוויגית של מיליארדי פרטים כדי להבטיח את שחרורם של יתושים זכרים בלבד. הכרח זה מהווה חסם לוגיסטי המונע יישום רחב-היקף של אמצעי בקרה אלה. ביתושים עיקר ההפרדה מתבצע באמצעים מכניים ובשלב התפתחות מאוחר בחיי היתוש - תהליך היוצא אל הפועל באמצעות כוח עבודה מיומן גדול, או באמצעות רובוטים מבוססי למידת מכונה בעלי עלויות תפעול גבוהות. פתרון גנטי לבעיה זו קיים בדמות זני הפרדה זוויגית. זני הפרדה זוויגית מתבססים על תְּשָׁנִיּוֹת גנטיות המתבטאות רק באחד מהזוויגים ובכך מאפשרים הפרדה זוויגית יעילה כבר בשלבי הגידול המוקדמים. עד כה, יצירתם של זני הפרדה זוויגית התבססה על בידודן של תשניות מושרות אקראיות ועל מאורעות התקה כרומוזומליים נדירים - תהליך תלוי-מזל מעיקרו שדרש כוח עבודה רב. בעבודה זו נרתמו ארסנל הכלים הביואינפורמטי ואמצעי העריכה הגנומיים המודרניים כדי לייצר זן הפרדה זוויגית ביתוש הטיגריס האסייתי *Aedes albopictus*. גישה הנדסית זו מאפשרת תכנון ופיתוח מושכל ומיתרת את התלות במזל ובכוח עבודה גדול.

בחלקה הראשון של העבודה, נערכה סקירה של פרטואר התשניות הידוע לספרות, בחיפוש אחר פְּנוֹטִיפ הולם; בסופה נבחר הגֵן השמור *yellow* הדרוש להשחמתו של מעטה-גוף החרק. באמצעות מערכת קְרִיֶסְפֶר הוצא הגן מכלל פעולה והתקבל זן יתושים בעל פנוטיפ צהוב בולט לאורך כל שלבי ההתפתחות. בבחינה של מכלול השפעותיה של התְּשָׁנִיּוֹת על כשירות היתוש לא נמצאה השפעה על קצב ההתפתחות או על גודל היתוש. ברם, הביצים הצהובות של זן זה הפגינו רגישות קיצונית ליובש. החזרת הפנוטיפ השחום התבצעה בהצלחה באמצעות מְחָדֵר החזרה סינטיטי המבטא את הרצף המְקוֹדֵד של *yellow* באמצעות שימוש בקָדֵם האנדוגני של הגן *hsp83*.

בחלקה השני של העבודה, במטרה להפוך תהליך ההשחמה לתְּלִי-זְיִיג, נעשה ניסיון להשתיל את *yellow* במקבילה האוטוזומלית של כרומוזום המין של יתוש זה. אזור עמיד לשחלוף, ובלתי מתואר ברובו מן הפן הביואינפורמטי שהתהווה על כרומוזום 1 סביב גן קובע הזכריות *mix*. באמצעות שילובם של כמה כלים השוואתיים מבוססי רמות כיסוי של סְפְרִיֹת-גְנוֹמִיֹת שונות זוהו בהצלחה 21 אתרים הקשורים בלעדית לזכרים, אך הניסיונות להשתיל גן מדווח בארבעה מתוכם לא צלח. לכן, לקבלת תאחיזה בין זְכָרִיֹת והפנוטיפ השחום נעשה שימוש בגישה שונה - בה הוסף *mix* למחדר ההחזרה הסינטיטי. ההחדרה של גן קובע הזוויג הובילה להמרה פנוטיפית מלאה של נקבות גנטיות לזכרים פנוטיפיים, וכך התקבל זן הפרדה זוויגית בו הזכרים (-המדומים) לבדם מציגים את המופע השחום התקינה, והנקבות נותרו צהובות.

חלקה השלישי של העבודה התמקד בהערכת ההתאמה של זן הפרדה הזוויגית לתפקידו. בהשוואה לזן-הבר לא נמצאו השפעות שליליות על קצב ההתפתחות או על גודל הזכרים שהתקבלו בזן הפרדה הזוויגית. לעומת זאת, הנקבות הצהובות היו במעט גדולות יותר, והפגינו קצב התפתחות איטי לעומת הזכרים. תופעה זו נוצלה בהצלחה להקטנת פרופורציית הנקבות בקרב הגלמים הנאספים. בניסויי הפרדה ידניים התעלה זן הפרדה הזוויגי על זן-הבר הן ברמת הדיוק והן במשך הזמן הנדרש לפעולת הפרדה. לבסוף, נבחן כושר התחרות הרבייתית של הזכרים המדומים לעומת זכרי זן-הבר. נמצא כי הזכרים המדומים מפגינים יכולת דומה לזכרי זן-הבר ביכולתם לאתר ולקוטל נקבות לצרכי הזדווגות. בנוסף, הם מסוגלים להשרות חסיונות בפני הזדווגות עתידית בנקבות עמן הזדווגו. ברם, הזכרים המדומים נופלים ברמת האטרקטיביות שלהם בעיני הנקבות לעומת זכרי זן-הבר.

על ידי ייבוא של פנוטיפ ממערכות מקבילות, יצירתו מחדש על ידי תשנית ממוקדת רצף והחזרתו בתאחיזה גנטית לזוויג - מדגימה עבודה זו את הגישה התכנונית ליצירת זן הפרד-זוויגי מודרני, ומספקת תשתית לבחינת התאמתן של תשניות עתידיות לצורך הפרדה זוויגית יעילה. מכלול הכלים והממצאים שפותחו בעבודה זו מהווים חשוב בדרך להתמודדות יעילה וברת-קיימא לנוכח איום אפידמיולוגי ההולך ומתעצם.

עבודה זו נעשתה בהדרכתו של:

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